

Co-creation conclusion report

Deliverable D2.3

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Deliverable D2.3

Co-creation conclusion report

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More information on the project can be found at <https://www.sender-h2020.eu>.

Executive summary

Financed by the European Commission under the H2020 program, the goal of the SENDER project is to foster sustainable innovation in the energy market, with explicit focus on energy services like demand response (DR), home automation and novel ways of producing electricity locally (prosuming) and trading between neighbors.

This deals directly with end use of electricity in the everyday life, and for this reason the SENDER project has as one of its main goals to enroll customers in a co-creation process in order to make sure the solutions developed are not imposed on end users in a top-down fashion, but that it also considers the needs and concerns of end users. End users are one of the central actors in the future energy system, and co-producing solutions with them helps ensure they will have a lasting and robust role.

The work undertaken in WP2 is part of the Analysis and Define steps of the SENDER project. Here, the co-creation is set up, and the focus on consumers placed at the center of the whole project. Through the co-creation steering group (CCSG), WP2 acts as a bridge between the technical parts of the project through dedicated workshops ensuring use and acceptance of technological solutions that are developed.

This report builds on D2.2 “Co-creation workshops report”, which presented discussions from co-creation workshops (CCWS) in detail and marks the final report from WP2 Implementation of the co-creation process. The data from the co-creation workshops, which are present in this report as well, are herein further elaborated on by an in-depth review of co-creation literature, as well as a detailed report on experiences and lessons from the co-creation process in SENDER. A second batch of follow-up data from end user input from the last CCSG is also included, the analysis of which adds to the extensive list of findings and recommendations that spring from the co-creation work in SENDER.

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1. Introduction

This deliverable marks the end of WP2 Implementation of the co-creation process. During the work of WP2, the co-creation steering group (for details on the CCSG please see D2.1), involving the demonstration partners, SENDER solution providers, other experts, and end users, was defined and convened. The work done by the CCSG laid the foundation for the development of a set of use cases to guide the technology development and implementation of the project based on a co-creation process. The final iteration of the resulting use cases can be reviewed in deliverable D2.4.

The purpose of the co-creation process has been to involve and engage end users with the SENDER solutions in order to bring their insight to bear on the technology development within SENDER in order to ensure the solutions we develop are user-centric, and that they allow for further collaboration between the project and end users.

In the work leading up to the Co-creation Workshops (CCWS), the use cases iterated in D2.4 were developed into a set of scenarios describing in narrative form how SENDER solutions can be imagined to possibly work in an everyday, household setting of the life of end users. This was necessary to start the co-creation process and provide end users with something to engage with. Based on current questions and challenges related to the use cases and the implementation process, another round of interviews was conducted in the fall of this year to serve as input from users to the second CCSG held during the writing of this report. This data is also included in this report, the analysis of which contributes to the final list of findings and recommendations from WP2. Finally, this report provides a state-of-the-art review of co-creation literature and, based on a reiteration of experiences and lessons learned, draws some conclusions regarding the co-creation process in SENDER.

All of this data has provided us with a thick description of end users' thoughts and preferences regarding a likely future in which SENDER solutions have been implemented in their homes. This is a future in which some new decisions about energy consumption must be made – and others may be left entirely to the solutions that SENDER is developing. Regardless, the final decision to let the SENDER solutions do their work in the households lies with the householders themselves. A wide variety of the many details and circumstances that affect these decisions are described herein.

As this is an investigation into the needs of users, this report will prove useful as input about consumer preferences on specification of concept for the SENDER implementation, i.e. WP3 on *Specification of a pro-active demand response system with consumers* and WP4 on *Policies, regulations, cyber security and data protection with consumers*.

Furthermore, the consumer preferences described in this data will be valuable for the work on technological solutions in WP5 *Consumer patterns modelling* and WP6 on *Technological development and interoperability* as well.

Finally, this report will provide useful data on what to take into consideration when implementing SENDER solutions, business models and enrolling customers in the demo sites, and thus be of value to WP7 *Demonstration and monitoring of the results* as well as WP8 on *Business model exploitation and roadmap*.

This report builds directly on the previous deliverable from this WP which was the D2.2 “Co-creation workshops report”. Some of the pages herein therefore have content that overlap with the previous one, and this report can be considered a stand-alone, final version of the co-creation reporting from WP2.

1.1 About SENDER

As the European Union moves towards sustainable energy, co-creation is the future of the energy service market. This entails a shift in the balance of power, turning customers into a new generation of collaborators and putting them at the heart of the energy sector. The EU-funded SENDER project will develop energy service applications for proactive demand response (DR), home automation convenience and security mechanisms. By engaging customers in a co-creation process, the project will shift DR from a reactive to a proactive approach. Consumer data will be collected and processed to identify typical consumption patterns, mirror them by digital twins (DTs) based on artificial intelligence technologies and aggregate the DTs' supply/demand characteristics.

2. *Demonstration sites*

This section provides a short presentation for any new readers of the three demonstration sites, also available in D2.2 and D2.4, of the three demonstration sites, as well as the expectations of the pilot partners towards SENDER.

2.1 *Alginet, Spain*

The Spanish demonstration site is based in Alginet, a village located 25 km from Valencia, in the east of Spain, with 13000 inhabitants. The distribution network in Alginet has a special particularity: it is owned by the end users through a cooperative. Currently, the Cooperative supplies 46 million kilowatts hour annually by means of 40 centres of transformation, with an installed power of 18000 kW and almost 6000 users benefit from the smart meters deployed by the electric cooperative, as well as other services and actions that the cooperative initiates to benefit its end users. Apart from the main basic activities of commercialization and distribution of electric energy, the cooperative group also plays a major social role in the town by investing and redistributing their benefits among the end users.

Our pilot partner in the project is Alginet Distribución Energía Eléctrica (ADEE), the local Distribution System Operator (DSO). In a context of continuously increasing, highly distributed renewable generation and the rise of e-mobility, ADEE is expecting new patterns of consumption and generation. The partner is thus interested in improving its forecasting as well as studying the value of Demand Response on congestion management and grid balancing. As a cooperative, ADEE is also interested in proposing new services to its consumers and thus taking the role of an ESCO (Energy Service Company): ADEE would like to promote individual self-consumption as well as energy efficiency and to foster changes in consumers' behaviors. Finally, as new dynamic tariffs recently appeared in Spain, meaning a potential higher electricity bill for end-users, ADEE would like to propose a service to minimize the bill of its consumers.

2.2 Weiz, Austria

The W.E.I.Z. demonstration site is located in the eastern part of Styria, about 30km from the provincial capital Graz. The pilot area includes the municipality of Weiz (11700 inhabitants), as well as the six neighboring municipalities and a total of 26000 inhabitants. The municipality of Weiz is strongly influenced by its industrial locations and its large leading companies. In this context, the municipality of Weiz is seen as a centre that provides numerous important functions (schools, shopping, authorities, entertainment, hospitals, etc.) for the households of the neighboring municipalities. The continuing expansion of the urban area and the resulting spatial planning developments regarding “working” and “living” in an organized development process open up special potentials of intelligent and sustainable development goals. With this in mind, numerous new projects and the systematic expansion of large-scale photovoltaic systems together with electricity storage systems, e-car charging stations and e-car sharing are being implemented in downtown Weiz.

Our pilot partner in the project is the Weizer Energy and Innovation Centre (W.E.I.Z.-FE), a regional contact point for the main topics “Energy” and “Innovation”. The main objective of the partner regarding SENDER is to optimize the electricity use in the region and can be decomposed as follows:

- To foster changes in consumers’ behaviors, in terms of heating, cooling and lighting, through remote monitoring/controlling and energy efficiency promotion
- To promote energy management systems to optimize energy efficiency, either by automatic control of devices (e.g., washing machine) or by sending notifications to end-users, in case they do not trust or want an automatic system
- To maximize self-consumption of the power generated by PV systems
- To propose smart charging to EV drivers (living in the municipality and commuters)

2.3 Otaniemi, Finland

The Finnish pilot site is in Espoo, Southern Finland, close to the capital city of Helsinki. More specifically the pilot area is called Otaniemi, which is a cape on the shores of Baltic Sea. Otaniemi forms a campus district with 5,2 km² area in total. Around 3500 people live in the area, but more importantly, about 15000 people come here daily for work. The area is composed of university buildings and several companies’ offices. Services such as shopping centres and restaurants are also found in the area. Otaniemi is also served by a subway line connecting the area to Helsinki city centre. In 2018, the Smart Otaniemi Innovation Ecosystem has been implemented in the area: its role is to manage the development of smart energy systems in Otaniemi (flexibility, smart mobility, district heating, data sharing, etc.).

Our pilot partner in the project is VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd (VTT), an impartial non-profit Research and Technology Organization. Through SENDER, VTT would like to study the integration

of EVs in Demand Response scheme and see the whole value chain run, from EV users with specific needs to (sub-)aggregators and other system operators benefitting from EV-based flexibility (e.g., for the Fingrid FCR-N market). SENDER could also help in minimizing the electricity bills of EV drivers and maximizing the use of renewable energy sources to charge the car, while ensuring EV drivers' satisfaction is met (EV charged at its departure time). Last, VTT is interested in piloting Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) to add value to any of the selected use cases.

3. *Co-creation: the state-of-the-art from the literature*

The following presents a review of co-creation literature, the most cited of which are summarized in Table 1. The area encompassing co-creation as a concept is not coherent and crosses between different approaches and paradigms of research. Much of the work is co-authored by a large number of researchers but some of it single or double authored, which may indicate differences between business, natural science, and social science literatures, respectively. No work in the table is older than 2010 and a significant part is published in 2016, which suggests that references in this area have grown rapidly. Nevertheless, certain core messages emerge from these works. It is possible to outline four of these in their turn and use a set of other research from critiques of co-creation and from the energy sector when it is relevant for the argumentation.

Firstly, co-creation is clearly a matter of concern and the subject of empirical work, agenda pieces, and some theoretical development, but is often found within the umbrella of research on transdisciplinarity, which can be understood as a broader modus of operating scientifically. In many articles, co-creation is only mentioned once or via an indirect reference (Brodie et al., 2011; Brodie et al., 2013; Chathoth et al., 2016; Xie et al., 2016; Hsieh & Chang, 2016). Transdisciplinarity appears as a new scientific paradigm that at the same time can be backgrounded by many of the publications (e.g. Trencher et al., 2014; Shackleton et al., 2019).

Secondly, those works that refer to transdisciplinarity use it highly flexibly. Across these cases, transdisciplinarity appears as an element of new paradigmatic “service science” (Ostrom et al., 2015) that advocates discipline-crossing knowledge production and research question formation. In another sense, the studies handle transdisciplinary learning within nature-based services (Frantzeskaki, 2019) and design-based approaches that can also be used in teaching (Kangas, 2010). Sustainability science is the context of much research works on transdisciplinarity (Mauser et al., 2013; Xie et al., 2016), however, another work uses the term to refer to crossing Western and non-Western knowledge bases (Parsons et al., 2016). Thus, the transdisciplinarity concept can conduct various work for the researchers involved and in fact, becomes more or less a synonym for crossing any established boundaries of knowledge production in most of the cases.

Thirdly, however, a dominant part of this most cited research comes from brand development, marketing, service innovation, and closely related fields. Within these contexts, the concept of *value co-creation* is drawn upon several times. As one of the founders of transdisciplinary service design, Lusch et al. (2016), explain this concept:

[...] value co-creation occurs through (social and economic) actors, involved in resource integration and service exchange, enabled and constrained by institutions and institutional arrangements, establishing nested and interlocking service ecosystems of value co-creation, which serve as the context for future value co-creation activities. (Lusch et al., 2016)

In our case we find value embedded in the structural arrangements of the SENDER project, and that successful co-creation within that arrangement makes use of present value to shape the future value. This specific type of focus on values and co-creation conjoins the foundational work in the co-creation paradigm (Ramaswamy & Ozgan, 2014). This is a rather new paradigm of business thinking set to synthesize a whole theory of value, especially when it comes to what is consumer value, hence the centering of the consumer.

Reference	Position to co-creation (methods, actors, and what is being co-created)	Position to transdisciplinarity (who is co-creating)
Brodie et al., 2011	Consumer panels; customers and consumers; co-creation of customer experience and marketing	Reference to new transdisciplinary marketing theories
Brodie et al., 2013	Online ethnography; customers and consumers; co-creation of customer experience and marketing	Reference to new transdisciplinary marketing theories
Ostrom et al., 2015	Roundtable discussions and surveys; customers and consumers; co-creation of services	A fusion of disciplines, unified knowledge production, and disciplinary boundaries reshaped or transgressed; service science designated as a new “transdiscipline”
Mausser et al., 2013	New research platforms and paradigms; scientific and non-scientific stakeholders; co-creation of science with society	Integrated research questions and joint pathways to sustainability, defined between natural and social sciences and relevant societal groups
Trencher et al., 2014	Qualitative social science analysis; government, industry, civil society; co-creating social, technical, and environmental transformations in pursuit of materializing sustainable development	Transdisciplinarity as a new research paradigm that is a background assumption of the research
Chathoth et al., 2016	Literature review; consumers and customers; co-creation of consumer value	Reference to new transdisciplinary marketing theories
Frantzeskaki, 2019	Cross-case comparative analysis; urban actors; co-creation of nature-based solutions	Transdisciplinary learning integrating societal and scientific practices; the research itself as transdisciplinary
Xie et al., 2016	Case studies and theory creation; firms and customers; value co-creation between firms and customers of services	Reference to transdisciplinary environmental sustainability perspectives
Kangas, 2010	Design-based research; teachers and children; co-creation of games	Reference to transdisciplinary research approaches
Hsieh & Chang, 2016	Survey method; consumers; co-creation of brand innovation	Reference to new transdisciplinary marketing theories
Lusch et al., 2016	Editorial-based piece; social and economic actors; co-creation of value	Propagating a transdisciplinary perspective on service innovations, meaning integration of computer and information sciences, mathematics and physics as well as social sciences toward theory-building
Shackleton et al., 2019	Stakeholder involvement methods; varieties of stakeholders (public/citizens, researchers, government, NGOs); co-creation of research and management actions	Interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary collaboration distinguished, but not explained
Parsons et al., 2016	Workshopping; indigenous and non-indigenous researchers; co-creation of knowledge	Transdisciplinary approach as moving beyond Western science and associated worldviews

Table 1 Summary of key most cited research on both co-creation and transdisciplinarity from SCOPUS

In the previous paradigm, individuals were represented as demand, rising and setting around supply; in the new paradigm, individuals and their experiences are the center of value creation. The point resembles insights from behavioral economics, social practice theory, and Science and Technology Studies (including co-production, user studies, participatory design, social learning and related perspectives), although no explicit reference is made to them. The notion of *value co-creation* designates how consumers of a service – such as energy utilities (Bonnemaizon & Batat, 2011; Heiskanen & Matschoss, 2016; for relations between co-creation, identities, innovation, and governance in energy development, see Elkjær, 2020) – receive value from the service that they use, specifically at the time of using that service. Businesses seek to co-create this ‘value-in-use’ and involve the customers in service design (Kristenson et al. 2008) because this can be a source of competitive advantage to the businesses themselves.

This brings us to a problem, which is the fourth message. Critiques have associated co-creation with a political form of corporate power that reproduces consumer life (Zwick et al., 2008). Without dismissing economic theories of value as such, there is a clear limitation to the kinds of involvement that many works allow. This is involvement in co-creation only as consumers or customers, including in brand development and marketing, but no way to engage in other roles opens up from herein. So, in this case, to be a stakeholder of co-creation means already accepting a consumerist role.

On the other hand, some works associate co-creation with extremely broad expectations around the missions of universities and science-society relations, resembling generic co-production that has become germane in recent Science and Technology Studies (STS). Thus, Mauser et al. (2013) advocate co-creation of science with society and Trencher et al. (2014) co-creating social, technical, and environmental transformations in pursuit of materializing sustainable development. While the business literature sees stakeholders narrowly only as firms and their customers, in the other end of co-creation research the stakeholders may include publics, citizens, researchers, the government, and non-governmental organizations (Shackleton et al., 2019) and all scientific and non-scientific stakeholders (Mauser et al., 2013).

There are many contradictions in these designations, but they need not be at odds. The question is just how one chooses to designate co-creation, what is being co-created, and the relevant stakeholders. To sum these works up, they mainly treat transdisciplinarity as an overall setting and co-creation as a norm, almost regardless of the research field. Meanwhile, very few works engage in any methodological development. As an exception, research done on stakeholder involvement in the study and management of invasive species can be mentioned here (Shackleton et al., 2014). While a wholly distinct field from energy – and more typical brand development of co-creation – the work raises useful critiques that are summed up here. Firstly, typical stakeholder engagement only has one type of stakeholder group (while consumers are not mentioned, this could apply to it). These stakeholders are engaged one-directionally and via methods that only gather passively knowledge from – most typically surveys. Thus, the authors suggest new types of stakeholder engagement, which encompasses the following:

- (1) improve co-design, co-creation and co-implementation of research and management actions;
- (2) promote social learning and provide feedback to stakeholders;
- (3) enhance collaboration and partnerships beyond the natural sciences and academia (interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary collaboration); and
- (4) discuss some practical and policy suggestions for improving stakeholder engagement in invasion science research and management. (Shackleton et al., 2019: 88.)

The authors point to co-creation of knowledge in particular and use co-design and co-development of projects as synonyms. The authors thus suggest a number of other methods than questionnaires, including interviews, workshops, and focus groups.

Taken to co-creation, this critique points out two things: First that even if co-creation is by definition a two-way value creation process (Ramaswamy & Ozcan, 2014), many works actually assume an overly passive role of the consumer that only gives information on their preferences when prompted. Second, transdisciplinary co-creation means a genuine attempt to collaborate beyond academia, leading to policy and practice recommendations, which those works that treat transdisciplinarity as the mere generic landscape context cannot achieve. This has implications for how to evaluate the co-creation process within SENDER, where users have been involved directly in the co-design and co-development of use cases and thus the project itself, and in a multi-stakeholder environment that demands a high degree of transdisciplinarity in practice.

4. Co-creation workshop approach: use-case methodology

This section provides a recap of the methodology, some of what was already described in D2.4, and which has been used to define the use cases to implement in SENDER. It also adds details about the co-creation workshops and data collection procedures that was presented in D2.2. Finally, it relates novel data on the experiences and lessons from the co-creation process as it was undertaken within the SENDER process, and draws some conclusions from it.

As described in the Grant Agreement of the project, SENDER applies a Quintuple Helix innovation model combined with a user-centric innovation development process as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: 5-helices co-creative innovation development and replication process

During the analysis phase, SENDER strived for the set-up of a co-creation process that placed consumers at its center as well as involving other stakeholder perspectives of academia, environment, government and industry on the SENDER solution. As a first step, experts of the consortium outlined state of the art insights on consumer-centric demand response systems through the presentation of generic use cases to the co-creation steering group. Based on the manifestation of the stakeholders and consumers preferences regarding those generic use cases and the SENDER solution components, jointly accepted and consumer-centric use cases for the SENDER implementation have been defined.

4.1 Generic use cases

As stated in the Grant Agreement of the project, SENDER has the ambition to put consumers at the heart of the energy market by engaging them in a co-creation process with other actors from the energy domain during the specification of pro-active DR mechanisms to cater for the consumers’ long-term incentivization. Use cases to demonstrate in SENDER should thus be based on the outcomes of co-creation. To ensure an effective discussion with stakeholders and final end-users, experts of the consortium presented a set of generic and technology-agnostic use cases for the Smart Home domain to the co-creation steering group to outline state of the art insights on consumer-centric demand response systems.

To select the generic and technology-agnostic use cases to present in co-creation, we screened several sources and conducted a first assessment to check that the considered use cases were in line with the objectives set in the Grant Agreement and feasible with regards to the core innovations and actors involved in the project. For a complete summary of the selection process, as well as a detailed overview of use cases, please refer to SENDER deliverable 2.4.

4.2 Co-creation process

SENDER uses co-creation processes to develop consumer engagement, ensuring that customers become collaborators in the design of energy services and ensuring the alignment of the use cases with the needs, expectations and concerns of the local population. These co-creation mechanisms are two-fold: co-creation steering groups and co-creation workshops.

Figure 2 The co-creation actors and process

4.2.1 Co-creation steering group meetings

A central tool for driving the co-creation process is the co-creation steering group (CCSG), which once a year gathers the main stakeholders of SENDER: technology and service providers, public regulators and end-users. These stakeholders mainly represent the three demonstration sites chosen for the project: Alginet, Weiz and Otaniemi, and is composed of both SENDER partners and external actors (see deliverable D2.1 for the list of participants). The CCSG gathered a first time in March 2021, a second time in September 2022, and will gather two more times throughout the project to ensure partnership with and insight from stakeholders of all the targeted audience.

The first co-creation steering group was dedicated to the definition of the use-cases of the SENDER solution. It was attended by ADEE, ECO, HPT, NTNU, VTT, WEIZ, SIN, TRIALOG, Väre and two end users from the Finnish demo site. This secured participation from demo sites, SENDER technology work package leaders, end users (partially), energy cooperative, DSO and supplier. Representation of aggregator and consumer organization was missing.

First, demonstrators and stakeholders were presented, after which the technological solutions of the SENDER project was presented by respective WP leaders. The CCSG then matched stakeholders with solutions according to relevance, and in parallel sessions divided by demonstration site, a brainstorming session was conducted to further iterate use cases and relevant needs and concerns. Finally, an end user evaluation was conducted to review the final use cases and results from brainstorming sessions.

The stakeholders involved presented somewhat different needs and concerns. This means the SENDER solutions are of interest to them in different ways. Notably, in Finland, VTT has several testbeds for EV charging and V2G, and are mainly interested in how SENDER solutions can empower users with timely charge rates, minimization of electricity bills and maximization of renewable energy use. WEIZ was focused on piloting direct connections between solar PV installations and households and other buildings and have an interest in turning households into prosumers. ADEE and Alginet, with their 6000-user strong cooperative, was interested in energy efficiency, peak shaving and maximizing self-consumption. However, doubling as a DSO, they were also interested in forecasting, flexibility, grid balancing and congestion issues.

In response to the presentations of SENDER solutions, many concerns were raised, both from stakeholders, technical team and end users. In relation to P2P trading solutions, challenges were identified relating to market regulation. The concept of digital twin especially raised some questions by end users, who had not heard about this before. Concerns related to details about information gathering, monitoring and privacy. End users were also somewhat concerned about their role vis-à-vis demand response solutions, and whether “responding” in this case would entail having to undertake any specific actions. Please note that the security and privacy aspects will be addressed in task 4.2,

which purpose is to define and apply a security and privacy practice. A Security and Privacy Plan (SPP) will be created in each pilot to analyze the related risks and propose some measures to provide the necessary cybersecurity capabilities. Please refer to Deliverable 4.2 for further details. Furthermore, Deliverable 3.4, presenting the IoT package to be installed in pilot households, includes a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) to ensure the data security and privacy of final end-users at every stage of the project.

The discussions ensuing in the brainstorming sessions identified several of the most important needs and concerns of the CCSG attendees. Based on the recommendations of the CCSG, six possible use cases were made that reflect on the variation in stakeholder needs and concerns. Through follow up work with relevant stakeholders in the period following the first CCSG and to the release of this report, these were reduced to five use cases, the final iterations of which are described in deliverable D2.4. The four main use cases are described below, however the last use case, related to additional services, was left out due to the workshop format, constrained as it was by online attendance and time limit. This decision was also supported since many of the technologies that would enable the SENDER core solutions, like monitoring by motion and temperature sensors, automated decision making based on machine learning and the digital twin, will be discussed extensively in the main four scenarios.

The second CCSG was convened in September of this year. It was a three-hour meeting that was attended by NTNU KULT, VTT, WEIZ, ADEE, SIN, TRIALOG, ECO, HPT and Väre. End user input was gathered before the meeting and presented in a separate session. This secured participation from demo sites, SENDER technology work package leaders, end users (partially), energy cooperative, DSO and supplier. Representation of aggregator and consumer organization was missing.

The meeting agenda had three main points. First, a session was held by NTNU KULT presenting end user input on the final state of use cases. Second, FHOOE paid the meeting a visit and provided the steering group with a thorough presentation of findings from the D4.3 Regulation and policy analysis report, forthcoming in M24. Finally, ECO held a session on “Defining meaningful KPIs for DSOs and aggregators” in order to provide input from the steering group on the demonstration phase in WP7.

Based on the experiences of the first CCSG, where it was difficult to maintain meaningful end user participation and engagement, the consortium meeting convened in Athens in May 2022 decided that it would be better to include a summary of user input gathered beforehand. This was managed in WP2 by contacting all demo sites and technology work package leaders in order to survey what would be the most pressing concerns regarding current use cases and their imminent implementation in the upcoming demonstration phase.

This input formed the basis of an interview guide for exploring user input on five topics, 1) the potential for users to provide additional information to the forecasting algorithm, 2) health and safety monitoring, 3) the possibility of providing additional information to users in relation to EV charging, 4) practical concerns regarding installation activities, and 5) general motivating factors for SENDER

participation. Finally, short follow-up interviews were held in the demo areas in order to collect data on these topics. The data from these 7 interviews were then compiled and analyzed in WP2 and presented for the CCSG, thus feeding user input back into the project on those topics where input was requested. The data is also presented in detail below (for more on these interview, it's results and analysis, see chapter 6. For details regarding the interview guide, see appendix 9.2).

The second session was held by FHOOE who had been invited to provide a walkthrough of the forthcoming D4.3 Regulation and policy analysis report. This session thus provided an opportunity for all stakeholders to get an introduction to the regulatory frameworks that are in effect in the three demonstration sites. This uncovered how they correlate (or not) with the energy regulations of the EU, the implementation of which have been decided but still take time to come into effect, and what this means for implementation of the SENDER use cases. Finally, ECO held a session which sought to explore how to designate meaningful KPI of the use cases in action in the demonstration sites, and thus how to measure the success of SENDER solutions to deliver on the use cases during demonstration. This was achieved by the application of a role-playing framework and an on-line collaboration tool, as stakeholders tried to imagine the questions and concerns external stakeholders may have toward SENDER solutions and their potential in real world application.

4.2.2 Co-creation workshops

During 2021, a Co-creation workshop (CCWS) was held at each of the three demo sites with end users and some local experts (from technology/service development and energy sector) recruited locally. In Otaniemi, Finland, the workshop was convened in the spring of 2021 and gathered 9 attendees, 3 of which were experts. The Austrian demo, convened by Weiz in the summer of 2021 convened 17 people, 5 of which were experts. The Spanish demo, Alginet, convened in the fall of 2021 and gathered 20 people, all lay people. In total, 46 people were involved in the co-creation workshops, 9 of which were experts. The groups were also attended by WP2-leader from NTNU, one representative from SIN and one, sometimes two from TRIALOG.

Demo site	Country	Month	Lay	Expert	Total	Expected
Otaniemi	Fi	M9	6	3	9	12
WEIZ	Au	M10	12	5	17	12
Alginet	Es	M14	20	0	20	12
Total					46	36

Table 2 Overview of the demonstration sites, workshop execution, and participants

CCWSs were recruited, convened and organized by the local demonstration partners. Within WP2, four scenarios were crafted that summarizes the use cases described in deliverable D2.4. They describe in narrative form how the SENDER solutions might realistically enter into the everyday life of households and forms the basis on which end user discussion and engagement is manifested in workshops. These

scenarios were presented to end users in each demonstration site in online workshops. The online format was unfortunately necessary due to restrictions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. The goal was to gauge acceptance of the use cases in their final iteration, and also to enable input from users and further facilitate the co-creation process. The sessions were held in the local languages and discussions recorded, whereby attendants provided their consent by staying in the workshop. Recordings were transcribed verbatim and translated by professional language experts. The resulting data was analyzed according to country and references relevant to the analysis were extracted from the discussion transcript using nVivo and coded according to the four scenarios. This created a basis for the analysis, which is presented in section 4. The four scenarios and attendant follow-up questions which were employed by workshop organizers are presented here.

4.2.3 Co-creation workshop results

SENDER has an outspoken ambition of casting end users as the central stakeholders in the project and has employed a co-creation method in order to secure end-user participation and contribution to the project over time, in addition to more robust technology implementation. In this case, the goal of the project is to develop demand response solutions that can make end user flexibility a reliable asset for balancing the grid, and where engagement from the part of the users is seen as necessary to secure the long-term reliability of technical solutions in providing this flexibility to grid operators.

Drawing on experiences from earlier projects (i.e., INVADE), SENDER has placed the co-creation process firmly upstream from technology development and implementation phases of the project, in order to ensure a strong link between user needs and desires with consequent solution design. The idea is good and can be interpreted as a sign that both the EU research programs, entailing as they often do large technical projects, have taken seriously the calls for addressing the role of Social Science and Humanities in such projects, ensuring perspectives of the citizenry is included into what are effectively society shaping endeavors that may have lasting impacts on the lives of the European population. This is also in line with co-creation methods, which are usually oriented towards bringing user experience with products into the development process in order to improve the future product experience of the users.

However, in this case, scheduling the co-creation process prior to technology development and implementation, which is beneficial for ensuring user input, none the less results in the process having very few technological products to engage users with. This not only makes user engagement through co-creation considerably more challenging, but it also lessens somewhat the usefulness of the methods for product development of the input that can be garnered in the first place. A consequence of this in

SENDER was a resulting need to immediately provide very clear definitions of what the technical solutions would look like once in place. To have such a clear idea of how the technology would look was deemed necessary for users to be able to give feedback. The project also already had work package tasks related to defining use cases, and so this became the starting point of the co-creation process. Thus, even though not a single material artifact had yet to be produced, the use cases were made to stand in as something with which users would engage.

The first iteration of use cases was created without much input from end users and was, as mentioned, more or less “pulled” into the co-creation process by the need for something tangible with which to engage users with further down the road. In practical terms, this was facilitated by a dedicated co-creation work package. The work in WP2 was divided into four tasks, the first of which was the creation of a co-creation steering group (CCSG). Under the direction of the task leader, a group of actors was assembled to represent innovation and implementation related parts of the project and different energy market roles (i.e., aggregator, consumer association, supplier, DSO, and energy cooperative). Demo partners were also participating, including two customers from each demo to represent end users. Finally, all work package leaders on technology in the project were included. The role of this group was to “generate insights on the needs and potentials of demand-side response services and technologies from the points of view of technology and service development, public regulators, and actual end-users” (SENDER 2020).

The first co-creation steering group meeting was held about six months into the project, facilitated by a task leader. The CCSG meeting was divided into four sessions, 1) presentations by demonstrators and local stakeholders, 2) presentations of technology solutions, 3) matching solutions and stakeholders, and 4) end user evaluation of use cases. In this way the first CCSG meeting served to bring together all the different stakeholders in the projects in a rather successful way, and the meeting therefore kickstarted both the co-creation process and the project itself. The result of the first CCSG meeting was a first draft of co-created use cases forming the basis of the task concerned with the definition of the use cases. Furthermore, it served as the basis for the interview guide that was employed in the consequent co-creation workshops.

In regard to the role of end users in the activity of the first CCSG, it needs to be said that including end users in a format like this, requiring as it did at the time a lot of interaction between internal partners resulting in a lot of technical discussion, served to challenge the engagement of users who were not always able to follow the rather technical discussions. The session dedicated to users did generate some input from users, but they were not feasibly primed to comment on the deliberations thus far, and their input into co-creating the use cases were limited. A lesson learned from this was that it could be useful to spare end users from too much technical jargon, and rather facilitate some form of mediation activity with which they can engage and provide input.

However, the co-creation steering group served well the purpose of establishing the co-creation process and involving the entire project into it from an early stage. It provided important input for the

co-creation process early on, establishing a strong starting point for developing use cases and engaging end users. The co-creation thus included many and varied representatives from both within and without the project, and both experts and lay people. This not only benefitted the project in learning about users, but also in terms of bringing together the different project stakeholders themselves early on. As mentioned, it also provided a very strong basis for the development of use cases, which was an important first order of business item in the project. A lot of work went into the use cases, and in this case, they were invaluable and central to the co-creation process itself. The work on use cases was undertaken in the same co-creation work package, under the facilitation of a dedicated task leader. The task herein was to define use cases for demonstrators based on the co-creation process. A central aspect of this part of the co-creation process was to liaise with the three demonstration sites, convening several workshops with them to better understand the characteristics of each pilot site and their needs and expectations towards the SENDER project.

Process of use cases definition

Figure 3: the SENDER use case development process and overview of the initial five-set use cases

The next step was the execution of co-creation workshops. The goal of the co-creation workshops was to add to the overarching focus of the co-creation steering group, focusing on the purposes and uses of the particular demand-side solutions in the demonstration sites. So, around the first quarter of the project, one workshop was convened by each demonstration partner and held online in each country in the local language and facilitated by a dedicated task leader. As mentioned, at the time these workshops were convened, SENDER solutions had yet to materialise in the demonstration sites, as the implementation phase was not planned before later in the project. The method employed then was to convert the use cases into narrative form, i.e., short stories with narratives that were reviewed by the technical partners and demonstration site owners before it was used in the workshop. Such narratives typically described what electricity consumption practices would be like in an everyday life with SENDER solutions acting in the household. Drawing on lessons learned in prior attempts at engaging

users with high level technical jargon, the purpose of these scenarios was to form a more suitable basis of engagement with end users, in order to be able to gauge user's acceptance of use cases as well as collecting inputs from them about their needs, concerns and general experiences on energy consumption in everyday life (for more, see appendix 10.1).

This was quite successful and provided end users with something tangible with which to engage and discuss. Unfortunately, some of the potential of these exercises was diminished due to covid and the need for using online workshops. However, discussions were lively and good results were gathered nonetheless, feeding into the continued iteration of co-creation of use cases and solution development, as well as providing a basis for deliverables related to mapping the results from co-creation and summarizing key recommendations.

Once the use cases were personalised with end-users inputs, they were re-converted into high-level specifications using the IEC 62559-2 template and the Smart Grid Architecture Model (SGAM). These high-level specifications as well as use case scenarios were then defined in close collaboration with solution providers, including descriptions of specificities for each of the three pilot sites.

4.2.4 Lessons from co-creation workshops in SENDER

The following observations have been made

- Co-creation needs a lot of facilitation and management
- Co-creation can provide a good basis for including not only users but improving collaboration between (technical) project participants and solution providers
- Co-creation in this sense may facilitate interdisciplinary work and produce more robust results useful to the project (in this case the use cases)
- Simply putting users and technical stakeholders in a room will not produce good results, some mediating activity needs to be in place.
- The mediating activity also needs to be co-created

According to the review, accomplishing meaningful transdisciplinary action requires meaningful user/citizen engagement, something which is not always accomplished simply by bringing the ingredients together. In this way, the transdisciplinary actions taken within this particular EU project perhaps took on mostly the form of service science, where through some interactions with end users in focus groups and interviews, a perspective from lay people were brought to bear on the project but where the knowledge gap between expert and user was sometimes too considerable for it to exploit the full potential of co-creation and meaningful transdisciplinary action.

Another aspect complicating this is the fact that as the products the users were meant to co-create did not exist at the site of the end user yet, they needed to engage with a kind of place holder in the form

of the use cases, which also needed to be explained to them for them to even be able to give their input. The question then arises as to what the object of co-creation actually is: the envisioned artifact, or rather the prompt itself. In this way, co-creation based on “translations” of high-level technical constructs may make us run the risk implementing a top-down education process, rather than a bottom-up engagement process, which in turn poses a problem of validity. Are you measuring engagement, or are people just responding to your prompt?

To conclude, co-creating an artifact requires facilitation and mediation between expert and user epistemologies. In working with a finished artifact, a meeting place is already available for these two perspectives within the artifact itself. However, the more an object is stabilized, the less room there may be for further development and innovation. At any rate, the use cases themselves as a form of knowledge were thoroughly co-created with users, and this represents a case of knowledge co-creation described in the review (see Shackleton et al., 2019).

4.2.5 Workshop methodology: summary of use-case scenarios

The following briefly describes the use case scenarios that were used in the co-creation workshops in order to gain end user perspectives on the SENDER solutions (for full interview guide see Appendix 10.2). Scenario one, “Maximizing renewable electricity use, reducing cost and emissions”, described how, with the help of SENDER solutions and faced with intermittent renewable energy sources, end users would be able to maximize renewable electricity use, reducing cost and emissions. In order to elicit responses about this scenario, questions were asked about how electricity was used and whether some of it was flexible, and to what extent users were interested in acting in order to synchronize consumption with local production and low prices.

Discussion and follow-up questions were asked, along the lines of the following:

- What are your main uses of electricity? Is this something that can be moved to other times?
- What if it reduces the network cost?
- Would you be interested in provided this service if it made it more likely that a larger share of renewables was used in a certain day?

Scenario two, “Building as a Battery (BaaB)”, was presented to examine the appeal of the Building as a Battery concept to end users. It introduced the building management system, it’s relation to the wider grid, and how it can provide flexibility services by employing the household as a battery, for instance by controlling the heating/cooling systems in a way that optimizes demand flexibility offering without disturbing occupant comfort. Questions were asked to gauge the interest in users of relinquishing control over certain consumption to enable BaaB.

Discussion and follow-up questions were asked, along the lines of the following:

- Are you OK with these decisions being made for you?
- Even if you would not notice any effect?
- If not, would you want it to ask you permission every time? I.e., through an app?
- Will you need to know in real time and approve for each instance, or is it fine if you can just review it at a later time?

Scenario three, “Peer-to-peer trading”, described how peer-to-peer-trading would work in a neighborhood, where the building management system once again made some decisions of how to distribute locally produced renewable power between houses in the neighborhood. Questions were asked in order to gauge how users considered the importance of compensation for allowing their PV to power the houses of neighbors and feeding back into the grid, as well as interest in prioritizing electricity output from neighbors for their own use.

Discussion and follow-up questions were asked, along the lines of the following:

- Would you need compensation for putting the electricity you yourself cannot use back into the grid? (PVs can be an expensive investment.)
- What about providing your neighbor’s house with your surplus electricity instead?
- What if it was the other way around? Would you be flexible in order to make sure you consume your neighbor’s surplus electricity?

Scenario four, “EV charging”, presented a case where the end user arrives home to plug in their EV for charging, and a busy afternoon of household activity ensues, raising the aggregate demand of the household to very high levels. At the same time, the building management system is requested by the network operator to aid in alleviating grid congestion, and thus to start scheduling several demand instances in the household like charging, water heating, and room temperatures. Questions were then asked to gauge end user’s sensitivity to the building management system acting on behalf of the network operator by rescheduling some demand (i.e charging, water heating, room temperature) in the household for short periods of time.

Discussion and follow-up questions were asked, along the lines of the following:

- What do you think about letting the management system take control of your indoor temperature for short periods of time?
- What if you come home, and the car is at 15%? You have programmed it to charge during the night to save money. Is this feasible?
- In general, how interested are you in being in control of these processes?
- What is needed in order for you to trust the energy management system to do it for you?

5. *Co-creation workshop results and analysis*

The following sections present results from the workshops and also the main topics from the discussions on each use case scenario in the form of verbatim quotes from workshop participants. Unfortunately, due to the online format and mixing of online and physical format, transcribers were unable to consistently assign statements to their owners. To remedy this somewhat, quotes are separated by designations indicating the country of the person stating it and a number indicating their place in the order of references for each topic, as they appear in the transcripts. The numbers are reused for new topics and may not indicate the same speaker. When a letter is added to the numbers, this signifies a conversation within the same reference between two people. It should also be noted that even though the headlines refer to the topics of the discussions that are referenced, some of the other solutions will invariably be taken into discussions where they are not the main topic of discussion.

5.1 *Maximizing renewable energy sources*

This use case scenario discussed how a household would be able to employ SENDER solutions to make sure they were maximizing the use of renewable energy sources, as opposed to not implementing any measures and simply consume whatever was available thereby increasing the chance of consuming fossil fuels. Of course, ideally speaking, mostly everyone was for this scenario. However, like evidenced by this Finnish participant, users may be wary of committing to any kind of flexibility or use-shift scenario without first getting a clear idea of the risk of inconvenience:

Perhaps, with regard to the issue of affecting one's own use and distribution of electricity, I notice that a lot of people are open to the idea, and that's how I answered, too, but at the same time I also thought that the inconvenience related to this should be reasonably small, of course. If you can influence or affect the issue, but it doesn't require any process diagrams or reorganization, then it's an option that makes sense, but, however, the reality is that life is complicated and time is limited, so if it takes a lot of effort, it's possible that people will choose the option that is the easiest, even if it means a slightly higher electricity bill. (Finland 1)

Differences of opinion did arise once the idea of having to make changes in everyday routines and living. For instance, a regular way of thinking about this is to try to create a mental map over which appliances in the house that would be available to offer up in case it would be a good idea to postpone consumption, thereby increasing the chances of consuming from renewable sources. This Austrian workshop participant said the following:

Just thought of the washing machine, that will probably be confined to just the washing machine, because I have to cook at noon when the kids get home. I can only charge my E-car in the evening when I'm back home because I'm on the road all day. The vacuum cleaner, which might run on its

own, we'd have a chance there. The refrigeration for cold storage at home, it runs all day, I can't control anything about that. You might have a just few appliances (Austria 1).

This participant observes that many appliances are outside the range for flexibility, whereas some appliances and consumption could more easily be imagined as possible to shift. The discussions regarding this issue were similar in the Spanish workshop:

[...] it depends on what we're talking about. If we're talking about the water heater, I do see flexibility, but for example, if we're talking about the oven, a little less, because of course, you want to do your cooking when it's eating time. I do have some flexibility, but I think a little less. (Spain 2)

Sentiments toward this were quite similar in Spain, where discussions were strongly oriented towards convenience. On the issue of shifting consumption to accommodate for renewable energy consumption, a Spanish workshop participant had this to say:

If it doesn't cause too many issues, too many inconveniences, then yes. If it were very inconvenient, then no. [subject asked to explain] I mean, if I'm taking the electric car and I have to choose whether to charge it now or later, if I don't have to use it within the next hour, it's all the same to me. I would wait until later. But if I plan to use it, I wouldn't wait and go out an hour later just so I can charge it when it's cheaper or when there's more flexibility – which is the idea. I don't know if I've explained it well. (Spain 1)

This is also related to the activity of showering, regarding which one workshop participant in Spain said that *"for me, even if the system tells me it would be best if I showered at X time, I would do it [regardless]"*. (Spain 4)

One issue that was explored in the workshops was whether users would be interested in shifting consumption for the sake of correcting grid imbalances. People in general do not seem very familiar with such a way of thinking, and those who are vocal about it will tend to be negative:

I would not reduce my consumption in order to reduce the load on the electrical grid. I don't feel like this is particularly relevant to me. For me the money part would be relevant. But on the other hand, these financial contributions are ultimately quite small in these, in one's electrical bill; at least for me, one thought I had was that I have to share is that, yeah, at least this remote working has improved the possibilities for flexibility because people are at home more. But before, there would not have been as many possibilities to be flexible with use of electricity. (Finland 2)

In general, some other topics discussed related to some facts of life which affect flexibility potential, like having kids and working from home or not. Furthermore, some users were in fact quite eager to have the kinds of capacities the SENDER solutions provided, and understood their potential easily for instance in the case of one pool-filtration and heating system:

In my case, I have a pool filtration system that's programmed so that it turns on at night, because it's cheaper that way. And also, the water heater, I've programmed it so that it doesn't heat up the water at night. It's what you've been saying more or less, no? (Spain 3)

As evidenced by this quote, in some cases users are already practicing load shifting and self-curtailing, and they understand the reasons why this is sometimes beneficial. Conversely, in another statement, the system being discussed was perfectly suited for load shifting by SENDER solutions, but this time the user had trouble actually seeing how this could be load-shifted at all:

We have direct electrical heating, so I have been wondering, since our heating bill in the winter is between 200 and 300 euros per month, can this be used to benefit us in heating in any way? Because, when the temperatures are below freezing, the heating must be on continuously. Can this system be utilized at any level for this? Because then in the summer, the heat is not turned on at all. (Finland 3)

This indicates there is some work to be done on some user's mental maps, which is something which may warrant consideration by the SENDER project in the implementation phase.

Finally, the discussion sometimes was related to storage, and how storage would indeed make the manual labor of load shifting less relevant, since renewables could be stored when produced and consumed at a later time: For instance, an Austrian participant had this to say about this:

It's not just about turning on devices. One must also consider, does one only switch on a device when energy is needed, but maybe also to store energy. An energy buffer comes to mind. (Austria 2)

This might indicate a "solution" to the problem of inconvenience, and that providing the opportunity of storage to end users may be a welcome offer when the alternative is that they would otherwise need to load-shift manually.

5.2 *Building as a Battery*

An issue that was often recurring in a fashion similar to the first scenario dealing with load shifting and RES maximizing, was that of who would be in control and the degree of autonomy of the SENDER solution.

It's becoming clear from the responses that it's okay for the system to make decisions for you as long as it does not affect your living comfort. At least not in a negative way. And then for the question regarding flexibility. There are answers in all directions. Some people would want to have

to give their permission to flexibility, and others would prefer to give control to the service. (Finland 1 – supervisor)

In many cases, participants voiced a bit of skepticism toward relinquishing control to an automated system. This does not mean that they did not appreciate a degree of automation, however they would need to be able to set some parameters this automation would need to follow:

You've said that the transmitter box has control over the system, but that the one really in control would still be me. So that I still control it, that I can say, okay in winter I'm home at 5 pm, and the heating system turns on at 4.30 pm. So, when I come home the garage is already well heated, and I don't have to sit at home in a jacket waiting until the heating system warms up. Because my digital twin knows when I usually come home. (Austria 1)

When discussing the topic of Building as a Battery, it became evident that most people do not distinguish the way this concept is manifested in life much compared to general load shifting and automation, similar to what was discussed in the case of maximizing renewable energy sources:

For example, if you are going to drive somewhere and your battery is dead [in the hypothetical case EV is an asset for BaaS] and it is necessary to charge it then this would not work in all situations you need to have the ability to override it in certain situations. So even if you let automation do the work you need to have the ability to override or bypass the decision. Or make settings for each device, so that this particular device can be controlled automatically but not the car; or it can depend on the day. (Finland 3)

Other people had no qualms relinquishing control in certain situations:

It would be a possibility, you receive a suggestion, now is the ideal time to start your washing machine. And by doing that you save energy in that time span. I'm not there today, turn everything down or do whatever you want. (Austria 7)

Even so, the discussion went on to reveal that even this would not be perfect:

Maybe I'll work 1-2 hours overtime and come home late, then it would already be warmed up. Great scenario. Despite having a cold, I still go to the office in the morning. I then realize it's not going to work out and I come home earlier, to a cold apartment. To what extent can I intervene so that it warms up relatively quickly, or can I not intervene at all? I should already have the control. (Austria 1)

Again, in a similar fashion to the discussion about convenience, some participants argued that if users deviate from routine, the SENDER system making autonomous decisions may produce inconvenience:

There is no advantage at all, if I've already gone home sick and then my management system says sorry to me. But if the temperature is lowered to 18 degrees instead of 22 degrees, for example, that's pretty uncomfortable. (Austria 2a)

However, some users expressed a distinct level of optimism regarding what an ecosystem of smart home devices could accomplish together with the SENDER solution:

That's exactly the discussion, I set the digital twin into action. It observes my environment and knows how warm or cold it is in my apartment. If I take this even further and say, now I also have a pulse watch, and this data flows into it, then the digital twin immediately knows that I'm not feeling well. (Austria 2b)

There is perhaps a slight indicator here of a possibility for inserting wearable technology and fitness monitors into the SENDER eco-system, thus producing something useful related to the health topic.

The discussion regarding the balance between control and autonomy was often developed into a discussion dedicated to how, in the case the user would be allowed any measure of control, this would be brought to bear on the SENDER systems. One respondent was asked how they would like to control the system, and answered like this:

I don't know, some kind of application. It doesn't matter to me, really. On the other hand, I would like to have something on the wall, because I hate the fact that everything is an application nowadays and you always need to have your phone with you, and you always need to be looking for it. Furthermore, if it were on the wall at your home, it could be both as an application and some gadget on the wall at home. And if you need to make some adjustments then even the children would be able to use it. I'm not sure how much this would affect everyday life but what I was thinking about was this is this would only be controlled by adults otherwise. On the other hand, I don't know where children would need to use it. But if you get a babysitter for example grandmother and if you were somewhere else then and outside it would be able to adjust those things Without you having to be involved making adjustments regarding something like the washing machine or something. (Finland 4)

A number of concerns is evident in this quote, which seems important to users, especially one that is somewhat experienced with technology use. Firstly, the phone does not seem to always be an ideal medium, since it is not always carried along with the users, and the user suggests the system should be able to be manipulated by people who are not "on-boarded" and where the installing of apps and creation of user accounts and sharing of passwords would not be ideal or desired, such as children, babysitters and other visitors. The solution suggested for this is something mounted on the wall that can be used to monitor and input simple adjustments by users other than the "administrator".

Furthermore, the discussions touched upon how users relate to what actually happens in the home when control has been exerted on the system. In other words, the system should not only cater for a level of control, but also provide a means of monitoring the effects of input:

It should have some default settings but nevertheless you would be able to watch what these selections mean in practice, and you would be able to change the parameters if you wish. But I agree with the majority here that real-time tracking is a little difficult. I don't think it makes sense for it to be beeping in your pocket all the time or having a device making noises on the wall of your house, but it would be nice to be able to modify or adjust settings as you... To see the effect of a setting after using it. It would be nice to be able to adjust them afterwards. (Finland 5)

Another issue which is touched upon here is that “beeping in your pocket” at all times of the day is something users are not interested in, and that a monitor system should not be invasive or obtrusive in any way. A level of discreetness to the way in which the system attempts to attract the attention of users for inputting some decision to load-shift or not, seems desirable.

Moving along the spectrum of this issue of the attention of users, it needs to be mentioned that some of them were also very skeptical about being involved in matters of the energy consumption of their home and appliances at all. This person, for instance, was worried that having to have to deal with building management technology like the SENDER solution was becoming obligatory in the future, and wondered whether it was possible to more or less opt out of it all:

Sorry can I ask, do you think is it inevitable that this flexibility thing will interfere like our normal life of normal people at some point at some level anyway or can it be so that these things will be handled automatically completely one way or another so that only the people that are really interested in these kinds of benefits economic benefits or climate change and possibilities to affect those things would have access to make decisions in regards to these flexibility things or is it inevitable that all of us will become used to having control of these things and you know so on? (Finland 6)

This indicates that for some people, spending a lot of time and attention on an energy management system at home would be for the specially interested, and that they would prefer this to be automated as much as possible. Again, this is reflected in the following quote comparing home automation with investing. Again, it comes down to making some simple decisions based on some information at a certain point in time, and then allowing oneself to “forget about it”.

Well, it's hard for me to believe that I would ever be so interested in those decisions as an active player in such a way that it would intervene in my daily life with all its questions. It's like in investing, in my opinion, even though there is financial gain that can be obtained, and the more time, effort and learning you put into it, the more you can get, I would nevertheless prefer a passive investment strategy, in which I go ahead with safe selections, and it doesn't affect my daily life, except... As a point of general interest, I would learn where I could save electricity or what things I

could earn from, and then learn about those and think, ok, do these suit my use profile, so to speak, and then make some individual active adjustments, or take the control into my hands in some certain category, but for the most part, I would prefer that the technology and intelligence be so good that I could be confident that 80% of the optimization would occur without regard for my active action. (Finland 2)

In the case of this person, it seems their ability to conscientiously forget about these issues, is down to being able to trust the system to optimize at least up to 80%.

For other people, the concept of a system autonomously controlling one's home also gave rise to some concerns about cybersecurity, and what would happen if for some external reason, like a disaster, a user's influence over the SENDER solutions would be incapacitated:

Another topic, worst case scenario what happens in case of power failure, a complete global failure? Is there blackout protection? Can the devices be accessed even in these instances? Is there a security system for the Sender-box? Perhaps I have young children or a vulnerable person in my care, I need warm water to wash them. I would be interested in that. How would that work? [...] Exactly, the question was, am I then autonomous? Can I still control the whole thing individually as a household, in some way energy efficiently? Or does it have no advantageous effect for me and so I say, okay, I'm just like everyone else with no electricity. (Austria 4)

The issue of even the physical protection of the box itself was important for some, likening the SENDER box in charge of one's electricity system to a safe containing valuables:

I'm very cautious about Cybersecurity. Namely, how is access to the transmitter box regulated, how strongly is it secured, how easily can I get in there? Do I keep my Sender-box in the garage or somewhere with a door that is open all day? Or do I encase it in concrete? (Austria 3a)

If an external person could access it and make it cold in your house, it shuts down and nobody knows why. Of course, that has to be secured and monitored accordingly. (Austria 3b)

Finally, a large part of the discussions, primarily in Austria, were dedicated to how the SENDER system connected to the house would relate to an island scenario, and security of supply in the case of a blackout.

Then we will be assisted by the Sender-box, that means the transmitter gets a signal and now I switch to emergency mode. That means I'm taking myself off the grid and the transmitter box automatically accesses my private storage and I draw my power from there until the public grid is back up. And the advantage of that would be that there really is blackout protection. With these transmitter boxes, we could potentially reduce the interconnected energy communities to the point where one source is enough for many. (Austria 5)

This was mentioned elsewhere as well, as some users exhibited a competence in this area, for instance in the case of this person who was already using solar PV to power the water heater and was on a mission to use locally produced RE to make them energy independent:

I already have solar panels installed for the water heater, but I was thinking of installing them also for the overall power supply, so the whole house runs on solar power. (Spain 1)

It is also worth mentioning that the discussion sometimes went in the direction of demanding solutions of the kind that the SENDER project is already pursuing, and which is more extensively covered in the next topic on Building as a Battery. For instance, one participant recommend this course of action:

Has there been any thought given to modeling behaviors within a single community and taking advantage of this in the optimization of its own electricity production and consumption? For example, if one family in the neighborhood has a traditional daily rhythm and another family that works late into the night could the consumption of the electricity produced be automatically evened/balanced between these example families? For example, if both families have solar panels, but they produce electricity between 9 a.m. and 8 p.m. One of the families consumes electricity from the panels between 9 a.m. and 2 p.m. and the other family uses electricity between 2 p.m. and 8 p.m. And if there is need for additional electricity it would come off the public grid. (Finland 7)

In general, the concept of BaaB caused people to have quite differing opinions and have discussions focusing on the balance between their own control of their house and the autonomy of SENDER solutions. Paradoxically, even though a level of control was desirable, interacting with devices in order to respond to notifications and manage settings seems less interesting to users. A universal solution that could be used by visitors and children was also desirable. Overall, an option to override automation seemed important, but a golden rule, according to one user, is an optimization of about 80% of resources by automation.

5.3 Peer-to-peer Trading

The discussions around the topic of P2P trading and the digital twin was characterized by some positive sentiments by participants but also caused them some confusion and the discussion would often revert to rounds of questions being asked to conveners. This could be an indicator that the concept in this scenario due to its cutting-edge nature, is something most end users have little knowledge about. Even so, people argued warmly for sharing electricity between neighbors, which in and by itself is a rather simple concept in theory, but that gets very technical in practice. This is a quote that shows some of the confusion which arose:

There is nothing more senseless than feeding the surplus electricity into the grid for many reasons, among other things. Also due to the question, whether the net in this capacity can always compensate. That means if I can decentralize using the electricity and pass it on directly to other households, without feeding it into the grid beforehand. I feed it into the net before, that probably contributes to network stability. On the other hand, surplus electricity, why should I not make it available to the neighbors? Whether it is regulated, or over the net. (Austria 1)

As is apparent in this quote, a mix-up quickly arises when discussing how trading electricity between neighbors actually works. Often the participant will prefer sending the electricity directly to the neighbor, bypassing the grid. But in reality, we may see a situation where the electricity will need to travel the grid to get to the neighbor anyway. Many participants would focus on how p2p sounded complicated:

In my opinion this sounds pretty complicated. To start selling to your neighbors. And maybe, in general, there are so many different levels of technology users. Would there be enough people who would participate? Maybe it would be easier to just sell back to the grid. There would have to be a lot of solar panels in order to have a significant economic impact. (Finland 4)

This participant has a sense that involving other people such as neighbors in a straightforward affair of electricity trading with the grid will complicate things. Indeed, this sense of complicatedness is also apparent in the following statement:

[Participant] Wouldn't that also provoke conflicts? If you promised me that I will have so and so much savings if I join you, and then I do not get as much as promised, because you consume it yourself? [...] the costs, there will probably be connection costs too, for these connections that have to be made?

[Expert] No, it goes through the public grid. No direct line, in between there are public power poles.

[Participant] Oh, then I understood it wrong. I thought it was directly connected. (Austria 2)

Furthermore, in some cases it was quite clear that some of the participants were completely unable to see the point of P2P trading at all, given that the contributions of electricity this would provide would be negligible:

And for me it's a little bit difficult to understand why we are even talking about such small units, talking about such close parties, such as neighbors etc. What is the meaning or significance of this? Is the point here to think that, psychologically, it would somehow be more pleasant to sell and buy from your neighbor? What is the idea behind this? To talk about someone familiar to us, as a party to a transaction? Is it a question of physical proximity? Is there some significance in terms of this technology? (Finland 11)

It was not always easy for experts and workshop conveners to answer these questions succinctly, so the discussions often revolved around general conceptualizations of how P2P can be implemented, ultimately provoking even more questions. In some cases *many* questions:

I've also imagined this model with the highway. Have a nicely developed highway, but the roads leading to it may be gravel roads. To what extent has that been taken into account? This is question number one. Question number 2: what is the legal situation? There is a change of tenant, for example. So, I assume that I do not necessarily have to be the owner of a house, but I can also be a tenant. What if someone dies, a whole new tenant comes in, what happens then? Do I have to pay costs, or am I obligated to participate in their renewable energy? Must I also attach solar panels to my house. That was three questions actually! (Austria 3)

This participant sums up just a few of the questions which would serve to bring across the feeling of inquisitiveness and somewhat skepticism that this whole thing would be too complicated to even know where to begin. The above quote related to legal matters, but of course there are technical parameters as well, further adding to the strain on grasping this concept. In these cases, the debate would circle around how electricity would be traded in practice between neighbors:

Have you thought about these kinds of models in which the electricity would be transmitted within your neighborhoods grid and in which everyone would have a storage of solar power and you would share the energy in a specific order, or would the idea be that you would engage in trade between your neighbors? (Finland 2)

The discussion would then revolve around “the logic of trading” and attempt to resolve whether people would engage in trade in practice, or if it would be more like a system based for instance on blockchain, measuring and monitoring the trade or sharing of electricity between the neighbors, automatically transferring from one house to another house and the blockchain constituting the bookkeeping between trades. Even one of the experts would get curious about what this would look like in the future:

There was a question for me that have we been thinking in our Sender Consortium about peer-to-peer trading, that is it going to be based on a marketplace where you could actually trade with electricity or is it more like blockchain technology such that the allocation or trades are automated events and the blockchain technology only keeps track of who has given what and who has received what. So, do we think that in this scenario the trading would be somewhat active [...] or would it just happen automatically, and the technology would only keep track of what has been happening? (Finland 3)

These kinds of questions produced discussions between experts and users that indicate that the experts in this case were not far removed from the users, as can be seen in this exchange:

[Participant] Apart from that, the question for me is, if there is only one producer and 3 consumers, how do I actually regulate it? What if there are 3 producers and 1 consumer? Who supplies the consumer and on what terms? Are there privileges on electricity supplies when it's sold?

[Expert] That will also be clarified, because do I have to take it or can I also say, I don't need it right now! That also still needs to be thought about.

[Participant] That was exactly my thought! (Austria 4)

When discussing the positive aspects of the P2P trading scenario, participants would sometimes point to the societal benefits of sharing between neighbors, and how “short-travelled electricity” would be resource saving. This is exemplified in the following statement made by an Austrian participant:

It would also be resource saving to join forces with the neighbors in pairs, to join together. Only one builds a PV plant, somewhat larger, both neighbors install a small 5kw unit or connects themselves perhaps to a larger system and rent a module or obtain the electricity from there, rather than that every single-family house in Austria has to install a PV system. It would be economical and resource-saving. (Austria 8)

In general, these kinds of statements were numerous in the Austrian context, possibly due to its rural geographical context compared with the other two. This perhaps also ties in with the discussions on some of the other topics, where Austrians again were considering how SEDER solutions could help with going off the grid and even serve as blackout protection.

Also, similar to the other scenarios, discussions often would return to the ever-central topic of convenience. Mainly, in the context of P2P trading, if trading electricity with your neighbor is experienced in the same way as in the conventional context, selling to a neighbor would be all right. If it was equally easy, it would make no difference:

Do you feel like there would be any significance as a matter of principle whether you sell to the grid or to your neighbors if it is equally easy? In that kind of case, it wouldn't matter. If it would be equally easy to me either way it wouldn't matter. (Finland 5)

[...] Perhaps the main point of these comment is that convenience is gold. If you don't have to think about your neighbor's schedule, or how you will share electricity with your neighbor, but would instead be able to get rid of your own surplus, and getting the maximum benefit of it, maybe that would, after all, be the preferred/favorable option. (Finland 13)

One thing is the experience or, rather, the non-experience of P2P trading. Another topic that was discussed was of course that of cost, money and settlement practice. Some users were quite “philanthropic”, like this one:

Yes, I would be interested. If I had solar panels, I would either give the energy for free or I would sell it, depending on the neighbor's needs, on his current financial situation. And if I didn't have solar panels, I would buy it from the neighbor. (Spain 1)

However, when it comes to money, the majority would prefer to sell their surplus electricity to the highest bidder. Selling to the neighbor was out of the question if the grid would pay better. However, both being equal, the neighbor was in fact preferred.

The truth is, if I buy it for 10 and then I sell it to the provider for 1, I would also sell it to the neighbor for 1, the same price the provider would pay for it. I would want to get the same price I get from the provider. I wouldn't be that... philanthropic. [...] If it were the same price, I would prefer to sell it to him. Yes. And my idea would be to go to a cooperative for co-generation of electricity, but maybe that would be a little more ambitious. (Spain 2)

In the case of Spain, the participants would rather talk about energy cooperatives than communities than P2P, as cooperatives were perceived to be a desirable thing to have among participants in order to save money and secure independence from retailers.

Sorry for being annoying, but this is something I had contemplated more than once on a personal level: doesn't the cooperative have a financial interest in promoting these types of things a little bit? Because surely the energy I generate will be cheaper for the cooperative than the one it has to buy from Iberdrola or the energy provider company, which could be beneficial for all members of the cooperative. And even further than that, which would be a more ambitious step, [wouldn't it be beneficial] for the cooperative itself to hire the workers and buy the solar panels so that it's cheaper for everyone? (Spain 4)

The concept of energy cooperatives seems to be important in Spain these days, and when discussing P2P trading, in the minds of participants the two would quickly eclipse.

Some respondents were worried about petty conflict about money with neighbors, and thought the faceless grid a good idea neighbors are dealing with a neutral actor or player and not dealing with each other even if would cost a more, but they would be a neutral party in between who would manage all of the agreements:

This is an interesting topic and even difficult to think about. I haven't even considered this before. It evokes many thoughts. In some way, the practical and technical capability aspect is interesting, but maybe what I think about is the social psychological aspect, the idea of a faceless grid might be easier because of how small of matters can create disputes between neighbors, and why there are boundaries between building lots. What I am thinking is that in these kinds of questions, there is not necessarily any limit to how petty people can be. So if there are new extra neighborly relationships on top of all of the existing arrangements, it may depend on the community how well neighbors get along with each other, and, in general how much they want to deal with other. (Finland 6)

Finally, when the relationships between neighbors were settled, and the many questions about the practical and legal aspects of P2P trading went unresolved, the discussion would gravitate toward people agreeing that this whole thing was weird, pointless, but not objectionable if it did not cause inconvenience and quarrel among neighbors, and that probably this whole concept, if implemented, could not exist at all except if people had nothing to do with it:

[...] but in my opinion, this is about the technology built in the background, or how regulation will change. I don't see these as becoming relevant questions to the end user. (Finland 12)

5.4 EV Charging

The topic of EV charging and its role as an electricity storage asset at the household was discussed last, and due to this fact, many of the concepts, sentiments and ideas about smart charging overlap somewhat with the general idea of a smart, automated house. And so, it is evident that many of the notions being discussed when it comes to the other scenarios, also apply here – in a way, the car is just another appliance. The idea that the car is not being used all the time, and that especially at night, it can charge whenever, as long as it is ready for the morning drive:

Maybe one thought I had was that if we are talking about delaying the charging of an electric car, is there some automation, so that if I plug it in in the evening and need a full charge by morning, and it recommends that the car should start charging at three a.m., will there be some kind of automation which would initiate the charging at that time? Do you know what I am trying to say? Will it be possible to automate it, so that it can be delayed, so for example, if I don't need something right now, like wash my clothing immediately but within two hours, can this somehow be automated? (Finland 1)

In the quote above, the user expresses a clear motivation to participate in demand response and make their EV available for this, and they are comfortable with the idea that they do not need their mobility at all times and that especially evening and nighttime has flexibility potential without causing inconvenience. One participant, talking at some length, indeed covered a range of issues with EV charging, indicating how this is actually more or less integrated in the overall demand response mechanisms in the home.

But as stated before, it is a very individual decision and I have tried out energy management myself, at home with the family, when I've said to my wife that we should time the laundry differently. She said the way she wants to do it is when it feels right. So, you see; certain things can be influenced, but certain things are not so easy to control in an automated way, due to personal habits. (Austria 1)

The participant goes on to admit they recognize the role of these scenarios for the climate transition objectives that are on the horizon for the long-term future, especially in terms of using cars as electricity storage:

On the whole, it has to be said that this scenario is nevertheless a very important one. The energy turnaround, the further expansion, the forced expansion with our goals for 2030, 2040, 2050 that exist in the long term. It has to be said honestly, we will only be able to cover this by including electric cars in addition to the expansion of energy generation. If you now look at the increasing registration figures, due to the incentive subsidies, etc. This means that these energy storage systems in cars are an essential link to energy transition, so that we can coordinate generation and consumption with each other. But as I said, everyone wants to have an energy management system, whether local to their home or higher level. There are already too many systems where everyone wants to have sovereignty and control. I see this as a problem. There will probably have to be a return to basic possibilities. (Austria 1)

It is, however, worth noting what is mentioned last in this quote, and which does resonate with the discussion around the peer-to-peer trading scenario above: certain aspects of the smart technology development are potentially starting to get complicated for some people.

Even though we could say the EV is just another appliance, the question of being flexible with one's mobility nevertheless sparked some of the most controversial statements as compared to the other three scenarios. First, we have the standard objections voicing skepticism and concern about inconvenience, like in the following quote:

I understand that. You have to hang up the laundry, there are logistics behind it, especially if you work. When do I wash, when do I hang it up? If you have several children in the household, it is not so easy. One person needs the computer, the other something else. First you have to get into a routine. (Austria 2)

But in addition to these somewhat mild concerns, more strongly voiced objections came up during the discussion of allowing flexibility into the realm of mobility:

I could comment on this, until now, the examples have been about insignificant personal sacrifices, something that does not require any kind of active thought, or giving anything up, but this borders on my comfort zone, it's possible that there is no need to use the car, but the idea may, nevertheless, be upsetting in principle, because you never know when there is an unexpected but essential need to travel, and you have the extremely expensive car in the garage it would seem silly or foolish not being able to use it to the full extent. (Finland 3)

This comment is quite dense, and touches upon several issues which could potentially have an impact on EV charging flexibility. First of all, it shows that the mere *idea* of not being able to take the car out when one might like (or need) to might be sufficiently off-putting for flexibility to be rejected here.

Somewhat differently than, say a washing machine, the need to go driving may instantly present itself, while laundry obviously is less prone to instant emergencies and more part of long-term routine and planning. A second point this comment raises is the fact that the car is an expensive asset, and so the “ownership” of it may be too strong to allow a person to “share” it with the grid. But, again, some people are able to see a compromise here, indicating that at least one does exist in many cases:

I myself thought that it depends on the car. But for example, my car has such a big battery that even with 15% charged I can go 50 km which should be enough for me, and I think that's enough to go to the store for example. You hardly ever have to take a long trip unexpectedly, and if the family has two vehicles are they both going to be electric vehicles? For many people it won't be, at least not for us. So, you could use the other one. And so, it wouldn't be necessary to use the electric one. And you could set the system so that if you have an unexpected need to travel you could tell the system to that you need to go somewhere in an hour, then you could interrupt the flexibility and allow it to charge, or something. How quickly do you have a need to leave immediately? (Finland 5)

Clearly some people can see a compromise, but it is worth noting that it depends on many contingencies: planning, big batteries, short distance to store, two cars, etc. Another, similar statement, also covers a rather long list of contingencies for V2G flexibility to be acceptable:

For me, if I can be sure that I'll have the service when I need it, that is, that I'll have the car charged when I need to get to work, if the system can prove to me that it's reliable, then I would allow it to manage it automatically. [...] as long as it ensures that at 8:00 a.m. the car is charged, or that I have hot water when I want to shower at 6:00-7:00 a.m. before leaving the house and at 6:00 p.m. when I get back, well then, it can do whatever it thinks best or what it wants to do. There's also an intermediate option, that it doesn't make all decisions on its own, but it also doesn't need to ask me about every single thing. (Spain 1)

Again, and similar to what was discussed in the previous topics, a lot of flexibility and control to automation could be given by some end users, but they have a long list of parameters which must be obeyed, in this case related to routine-based activities and time of day. In any given scenario, a lot of consideration would need to be given to how users can easily input and control these parameters.

Furthermore, the discussions show that even though people may be positively inclined to allowing their car to act in a V2G capacity, this would of course require them to leave the car in the driveway:

There was one sentence which mentioned so-called V2G or vehicle-to-grid, in which [the SENDER box] even considered whether it should discharge the car battery and use it to cover the house's electrical consumption. [...] I don't have anything against it. The only problem is I don't have an electric car. But in the future, it would be a good solution. To store the electricity in it during the day. But the only issue is that the car would have to be in the yard during the day, that's probably the only problem. But a good solution in my opinion. (Finland 7)

So, even though being positively inclined (and not owning an EV), the main problem here would be to have the car present, which of course for most people is not an option if they need to go to work – unless, of course, the work is at home:

This is not very familiar to me, I have heard some bits and pieces from others, but I'm not very familiar with it. For example, how it would work in practice. But I see it as a possibility. For me for example I always work from home now, so my car is always in the yard. (Finland 8)

In summary, the discussion on EV charging and V2G has given evidence that many people are quite skeptical towards this because it infringes on the experience of mobility given to them by a costly investment into the expensive (and delightful) asset that is their car. A lot of people are willing to compromise, but this is dependent on both physical contingencies, like battery size, local geography; and routine-based activity, like when they need to shower and go to work.

6. User input for Co-creation Steering Group meeting #2

Based on the experiences made from the first Co-creation Steering Group, the decision was made by the consortium in session for its fourth meeting (Athens, May 2022) to introduce input from end users to the CCSG in the form of data from a preliminary round of interviews focused on issues regarding the current state of the use cases. In the days leading up to the CCSG, each demo conducted interviews with several end users each, in order for the user inputs to have a broad and representative voice at the CCSG. The interviews were centered on topics that solution providers and demo organizers reported as important to know more about at the time of the CCSG.

Country	Demo	Interviews	Duration	Designation
Spain	Alginet	1M, 2F	3 x 20 min	(An)
Austria	WEIZ	1M, 1F	2 x 20 min	(Wn)
Finland	Otaniemi	1M, 1F	1 x 40 min	(On)
Total		6	140 min	

Table 3 Overview of the demonstration sites, interviews, and participants

An interview guide was produced on the basis of this, with 5 topics in total, across three scenarios and two question categories. The creation of the scenarios followed the model of the scenarios developed for the co-creation workshops, albeit with a smaller scope. The first scenario in this round of interviews was the prospect of users adding more information to the forecasting algorithm, so that it could be more effective in its predictions of flexibility availability. The second scenario that we explored in this round of interviews, was the prospect of having the sensory suite that is installed in households also allow for health and safety monitoring. For instance, if no one is moving at a time when the presence of house occupants would be predicted, this could indicate distress. In the opposite fashion, a recorded presence when everyone is predicted to be absent from the household, this could indicate unauthorized entry. The third and final scenario regarded EV-charging and the provision of additional information through a separate UI.

The two final categories were first oriented around exploring how people would tolerate in practical terms the many instances of intervention that installing and hooking up the SENDER solutions within the household represents during the start of the demonstration phase. Finally, the last category explored the motivations of people to engage with SENDER, becoming a participant, and using the SENDER solutions. The following explores some of the most notable interjections and comments that users provided during the interviews.

6.1 Additional information to the forecasting algorithm

The first topic that was explored in the interviews, was if people would be able to provide additional, supplementary information to the SENDER forecasting algorithm. Suggestions for users in this case included plotting in future plans, whether they be business or pleasure related, so the algorithm could better predict when flexibility would be available. In general, respondents agreed this would be a good idea, just not very applicable to themselves:

No. Moreover, based on what you're proposing, the profile you're looking for is a consumer who has some regularity in his electricity consumption. See, I work in shifts that keep changing. You know? I could go into work in the morning, in the afternoon, at night... I could be working on Saturdays, Sundays, Mondays, then have two days off Tuesday and Wednesday... So, that means the system will be going crazy. [...] I do have a monthly schedule, but it often changes because we may exchange shifts between colleagues, because something came up, you know? (A1)

In general, many of the respondents were not keen on this idea in their own lives, as they did not think they would be able to predict their own plans for very long into the future, or that they had too much of an unpredictable schedule in general. However, some people found it ok as long as it would be easy, and did not take a lot of effort to program:

That would be a great advantage, if you can control it yourself, that you can precisely control such unpredictable events, let's say, or if you are on holiday or if, as you say, you work at home. Ideally, you have a fairly simple system and it's all about simplicity. [...] And that means there has to be a simple system or a simple way to tell Sender that I'm at home or I'm not at home. And ideally you pre-programme it so that you say okay, when I'm at home, I'd like this, maybe this degree of heating. If I'm not at home, then please reduce the temperature by a few degrees. (W1)

Many of the responses were similar to the one above and gives us an idea that the somewhat technology savvy end users involved in projects such as this have learned to respond along the lines of experts with the line "it has to be easy". Thus, having people wrap their heads around routinely feeding future plans into an algorithm made them consider this to be too much work. Instead, their responses went towards a more "easy to use" solution, such as a simple home/away-switch:

I'm sure there are some people who are a bit more interested in the detail and might want to do that using the settings. But I think the majority of people want two modes, the first mode: I'm at home, I want it the way it always is, and the second mode has an on/off switch, please off, I'm away, shut the system down. So for many people, I think, a smart home setup has to be the simplest thing: I leave the house, I press a button and all the energy systems and electricity uses are shut down, except for the most necessary ones such as fridge and so on. (W1)

A modulation of the idea that users themselves would need to input their plans into an algorithm with the help of an app or similar UI, and this suggested that they would be able in this scenario to link their calendars (e.g. Outlook) with the algorithm, implying this would be easier since it is providing information they would already have to input somewhere. In short, many thought that this was a good idea, but again not very applicable to themselves. The reason: since they don't really do calendars:

Yes, it would be possible, although the majority of users don't have a calendar that could be integrated exactly. That would be a rare case. If I am someone who regularly enters everything in a calendar or perhaps keeps a private appointments diary – many people probably do it manually, if at all –, then that would perhaps be an add-on, but I don't think that would be effective for mass use. [I would not use it] Since I don't really do calendars... (W1) [...] It's a nice idea but I wouldn't feel comfortable with it. [...] The option is okay, but I wouldn't use it. [...] I don't have a calendar. (W2)

As the case was with the simple idea of inputting one's own plans, respondents in this modulated scenario with calendar linking once again kept reducing this idea to "a simple button" that could say to the algorithm whether a person is home or not.

At least for the Outlook and school calendar, I say absolutely not. Either the app, or with regard to the holiday mode, is there a button on the device at home that we could press to indicate holiday mode, or what do you mean? [...] In my opinion, with regard to the app, one option that was missing is a device at home, where I can press to indicate that now I'm home, and then now I'm leaving, and you could feed it some time schedule, kind of like a timer. (O1)

In this case it seems as far as people are willing to go is providing the algorithm a notice when they had decided to return home from wherever they were. Conversely, this could presumably be applied in a scenario when they are leaving later in the day. When discussing using an app or other platform to provide this supplemental information:

Most of the time, daily life is quite routine, with regard to who is at home etc. I think some kind of a calendar function would also work, too. [...] I wouldn't necessarily feel like starting using one for this purpose at home, somehow, the way I see it, the easiest way would be some general program that would be easy to adjust or set. [...] I think it would be great to have that kind of a possibility. To be able to send a message home, that my plans changed, I won't be on holiday all day, or out of the house all day, then my house won't be cold when I arrive. Instead, the heating would be ready. (O2)

The lack of perceived structure in life is too big a barrier to give more information about future plans to an algorithm

And I might decide on the same night, that I am going somewhere, and will be gone for the night, or whatever. I don't have a regular daily routine, during which time I would like it off. For me, the algorithm wouldn't work because if I myself don't even know my life, the algorithm certainly

doesn't know my plans. [...] when I reflect on whether or not I would have the energy to do this, I think a financial carrot would be good; saving electricity is good, but for example, if you commit to doing this for a certain amount, then you get a lower priced electricity contract, for instance, something like that. (O1)

6.2 Health and safety monitoring

In the scenario where we presented the idea that the sensors and algorithm could be used to detect if a person were in distress or if there was an unauthorized person in the house, people were of mixed opinions, where for instance this respondent was quite skeptical:

I'm not liking this project at all. I find it very intrusive. [...] I just think that... I don't know. I thought what it would do is analyse the energy consumption of household appliances and see if it deviates from the norm. But to think that the consumption is related to a person, and for it to know when that person is at home and when they're not, and which activities that person is engaged in... (A1)

In general, people had some trouble understanding the concept of the digital twin in this case, and that data about movements within the house would not be linked explicitly to an activity or to a person. This indicates that people would need to have this quite thoroughly explained to avoid initial negative impressions with the functionality of the SENDER solutions.

Regarding how people would like to be notified in the case this kind of system was in place, a general sentiment was that being given push notifications if there were indications made by the SENDER system that there was an intruder in the home was not very desirable, since notifications were not considered a secure or reliable enough mode of communication in the case of home intrusion. Besides, the fact that there was a total of four persons living in the home there would be a lot of traffic to keep track of, not to mention who would be receiving and responding to notifications:

I wouldn't be interested in that, but... [Would prefer] A WhatsApp message, an SMS, or whatever. [...] Because you never know when you're going to get a notification. So as long as they're not impertinent alerts, at inconvenient times... [...] But there are four of us at home. [...] But it's something that it needs to know, then, that there are four of us. My daughter has gone to Germany now, but when she comes back there will be four of us. (A2)

Yet another respondent was skeptical towards this and though it might create more problems than it would solve, in for instance a case where one would like to lie down and this would cause the system to conclude there was need for assistance:

It's a very sensitive issue, I'm just thinking, what could come out of this if one time, I don't know, let's say I walk downstairs in the afternoon and the system works okay. Nothing moves, I might have fallen somewhere and passed out. I don't know. [...] let's say, older people who say, okay, I have this option here, that an emergency call is automatically sent if something is wrong. On the other hand, it might also be negative that it creates more of a fuss than it actually helps. But as I said, if you go downstairs, sleep and then nothing happens and then automatically the alarm is raised. [indistinct] You have to be very careful. (W1)

Likely, a person would be worried if the SENDER algorithm notified authorities of problems when it was only the occupant taking a nap. Then, as suggested by the interviewer, if we turn this around and the system looks for movement when there should be none, this was not received as a great idea either:

That might be a benefit. But when I think about my situation, if you have pets, for example, it might also be a bit of a problem. If the cat or the dog runs through the flat or through the house and the system recognizes it and then says that something is moving. Maybe that should be looked at. (W1)

In all likelihood these are challenges that may be overcome should a solution providing this capability be introduced in the SENDER package in time, however the concerns of end users as outlined above would still need to be addressed. Another respondent was skeptical because they thought this did not belong in the same conversation as electricity, maybe unless it was a service provided for free:

I think this goes into a separate category than the electricity issue. In my opinion, these are different issues, and I would have to think entirely separate on a safety system. [...] if I want a security system, I would turn to Securised or whatever that company's name is. In any case, I would prefer to use of those... on the other hand, if it would be a nice addition if it was included in the price but I would not pay extra. (O1)

In general, the kind of health and safety monitoring that has been considered for the SENDER solutions so far does not seem to find any good footing when described in the interview sessions. However, one of our respondents had a suggestion regarding the use of these sensors:

As a matter of fact, I just thought of something; not home security as such, but more like a water damage function, or something like that, might be something I would be interested in. Maybe some kind of intelligent, I don't know about fire, but maybe a water damage function, that might be interesting, or perhaps a frost alarm in the winter, if your house got cold. Something semi simple. [...] Yeah, something like an electrical outage alarm. I am not interested what is moving in a room, but something like a water damage, a leak, or water flow. (O2)

But again, as mentioned by the respondent above, in case of a security situation, there should be a secure and reliable way of notifying, and a push notification or text message is not good enough

In my opinion, that water damage function would sound smart, and in my opinion if there is some water damage, there should be a phone call. Because when we're talking about security issues, in my opinion... [...] a phone call would then be the best way to reach someone. Because it's so serious that you should get the information immediately, ok, there is possible water damage in my home. If there's a text message, I may not necessarily notice it. (O1)

6.3 EV charging and additional information UI for users

When trying to gauge the interest for additional information for EV charging, some respondents reported they would consider issues of information overload:

I imagine every car has a computer system on board that tells you, at this charging station you've charged I don't know how much. I think that's just doubling the amount of information. And the problem is that, at the end of the day, so much information is suffocating, and you don't even look at it. [...] I just think it's double the amount of work you have to do. [...] What I'm telling you is... well, for example, I have a car but one that uses petrol. And your mind knows perfectly, it has to remember where you've fueled it. And what I understand is that cars tell you, you have 25 minutes of petrol left. So, the electric car also has to tell you, now you have 15 minutes left. It's the same thing. I think it's an excess of information that I don't [need]. (A2)

Another user also considered addition information and user interfaces a bit excessive, since in most cases cars usually provide this kind of information already. At least, this is not interesting if it does not have some extra functionality:

You have to look at the interfaces, because classically the car takes care of whether you are charged or not. On the other hand, of course, a remote control might be useful. If you say okay, maybe the electricity price is too high, please stop charging, it would be possible. The question is always whether it doesn't become too complex. The whole system. [...] It always depends on the interface, that it is very well linked, because there are probably already apps with which you can control it. And if you can implement that in the simplest possible way and you can then control it via the app, please charge or please stop charging [...] (W1)

Finally, this kind of detailed management would not be interesting in the case where you can always rely on the night times to be cheap:

At first, I charged during the day because I have solar panels and got profitability from that. But nowadays I have a low-priced electricity contract, it makes more sense for me to sell that back to the grid and charge my car at night. So nowadays I'm only charging at nighttime. [...] But if the price of electricity were super high at all times, for instance, then that kind of optimization would be more relevant. (O2)

And from this quote is possible to see why this is relevant if there is no delay from the moment of plugging in the EV:

But if the price of electricity were really high, some kind of timer function should be the option, so that I would have to get up and plug it in. When I get out of the car, I just plug it in and that's it. But if I'm charging in a public charging station, it means I have to be present and plug it in in order to continue on my journey, go to the shop, whatever. In my opinion, in those situations, it wouldn't be relevant at all. It costs a certain amount to charge, and I start charging it, to the extent it charges in that amount of time. I don't see optimization in that situation as being sensible at any level. (O1)

6.4 Home intervention – practical issues

When it comes to the practical issues regarding the installation process, there was first of all some evidence that the talk of boxes, panels and fuses can be a bit confusing, and people don't always know if they are talking about the same thing. For example, when having a conversation about installing the SENDER system, in practical terms having installers install the box, that they use one of your outlets, that it would connect to your internet, and other issues (see Appendix 10.2 for full checklist).

I: And with regard to giving the installers access to the electrical panel and electricity meter?

R: They already have access to it, no?

I: I suppose they would connect some pins to the meter to measure the electrical current flow. For example, if you have a panel where you have your household appliances, to see—

R: Ah, you mean inside the house. You don't mean the electricity meter, but the electrical panel that you have inside the house.

I: Exactly.

R: Ah. Well, I wouldn't have a problem with that. (A1)

However, respondents were also a bit skeptical regarding the amount of physical intrusion by the installers and the equipment, as represented by this statement:

Um... I don't know. It would depend on where they would want to install it and what it requires. I don't want holes in my walls. Then, I think it would be complicated. I think they won't let me give you permission. (A1)

But when it comes to installers going over equipment already existing within the household in order to look for compatibility issues, this was generally welcomed, indicating opportunity for making a positive impression in the early phases of the demonstration and implementation phase:

No, I wouldn't mind at all. It would be great if it would tell me if it's working or not. (A1)

People also mentioned in this part that they were interested in knowing how much data and electricity the installed equipment would use. If anyone has a problem with something and high consumption occurs, they will probably blame the SENDER equipment even if it's not the reason for the fault:

I will say the same thing. I have to know the electricity it's going to use. If they install something and I suddenly have a much higher electricity usage... I want to know the consumption and I want to know also how much data it's going to use. [...] I want to know what could be an inconvenience to me and what benefits it could offer me. I need to know if it's going to disturb... [...] If it's going to be a great inconvenience, well then, no. (A2)

The following conversation points to some interesting consequences. If users have modern homes with modern equipment, they might be skeptical towards having them replaced. If it's quite newly installed, this may give rise to reluctance because of the investment already having been made on part of the user. Also, if they are used to controlling everything themselves, if new equipment is installed, this may result in the loss of control.:

R: I have 49% surplus, even though I have the house cool all day, from the time it's plugged in until we're done with it.

I: Okay, so you already have quite a smart home.

R: Yes. You see, the house was built only four years ago. Well, five soon. It's quite new.

I: All right. Would you agree to someone performing a check of equipment and intelligent devices? [...] check whatever devices you have installed, in terms of home automation, and the rest of it.

R: I don't have anything truly automated.

I: Because you are at home and you control it yourselves.

R: Yes, of course. (A3)

One respondent was not concerned about the use of electricity outlets, but had concerns regarding lighting:

Um, with the right distributors it's probably not an issue. The question is then maybe more whether these devices are then also plugged in for example overnight and do they flash or light up. That could be a problem for pets, for example, because you don't want individual rooms to be lit up at night. That would probably have to be looked at. It might cause a bit of a light nuisance for some people. [...] We

have a WLAN repeater, and it flashes all night. And that's just something you don't necessarily want in your room. If it's somewhere in the office, or switched off at night, then it doesn't matter. But you would have to look at it carefully. (W1)

Finally, there was one interesting bit about internet connection that could pose some issues, as evidently not everyone has Wi-Fi in their homes:

My first comment is that it requires Wi-Fi, and I, at least, don't have Wi-Fi. Because I always share my internet access from my phone, and I have done this for ten years. It works, so I have not had any need for Wi-Fi because I only use my laptop and own phone and sharing the phone's internet is sufficient for it. So I would not have Wi-Fi for that device. (O1)

6.5 *Final questions. What motives?*

The final group of question posed to end users in the second round of interviews was about what kind of motivation users have for joining SENDER and using the technological solutions in the first place. The question was three-pronged, and was posed to explore if users would be committed to SENDER due to environmental reasons, economic incentives, or because they were interested in contributing with congestion alleviation to make the grid more robust. In general, people would weigh the economic incentive up against their environmental commitment:

I suppose I'm more of an idealist because when I installed solar panels they weren't very cost-efficient. Now that electricity prices have gone through the roof, solar panels have started making more sense financially. But I think that, at the end of the day, the electricity bill factor is what motivates most people. If I didn't think I was going to recover my investment at some point, even if it was over a very long period of time, I wouldn't have installed them. So, I don't want to portray myself as too much of an idealist. (A1)

The following statement describes something similar, but seems to add some sensitivity related to whether or not measures implemented by SENDER may have an effect or not - meaning economic incentives are the main measure, but that using electricity in a more sensible manner, like sharing a surplus with neighbors, is also a motivating factor:

I think at the moment in the current situation, both for me and for the majority of people, probably reducing electricity costs, because at the end of the day for everybody, that's the most noticeable issue in terms of the output from the project. On the other hand, if you can exchange energy with your neighbours, maybe through energy cooperatives, etc., that would be an additional benefit. But at the end of the day, if lower electricity costs are incurred as a result, then it works. But if

nothing is achieved, and the electricity costs remain the same, then the project will probably be something just for hobbyists, but not for the general public. (W1)

At last, the final statement presented here about motivation gives a strong indication that environmentalist motivating factors are relevant, but that at a certain point the issue of cost can become so significant, it reduces the ability to choose anything else:

Well, the biggest is the electricity bill. It's the only thing...I mean the others are fine bonuses, but the electricity bill is it. (O1)

Yeah, maybe I have to say electricity bill matters the most. Maybe that one is too abstract, the electrical grid. Environmental friendliness does matter; sometimes I have selected an electricity contract wherein the electricity is produced in a more ecologically friendly manner. So yeah, to some degree it, too, matters. (O2)

But, if at some point it becomes too expensive to be green, the financial reasons outweigh all others. Environmental friendliness is very important to me, too, BUT if the prices is super high, I don't care what coal is used to produce the electricity if it means my bill is 400 instead of 600 euros. This is so significant in a financial sense. At that point I don't have a choice. (O1)

7. *Summary of findings and recommendations*

The following is a summary of the findings, presented in short bullet point form. Sections 7.1-4 present findings from the co-creation workshops. Sections 7.5-9 present findings from the co-creation interviews undertaken for the second co-creation steering group meeting. In general, it can be noted that some of the input from end users are based on faulty assumptions on their end and, as discussions were semi-structured, some use cases belonging to certain topics would find their way into other topics. Even though comments and discussions sometimes were based on incorrect assumptions about the SENDER solutions, they should not be dismissed as they give the SENDER project valuable insights into what users do *not* understand, and where attention in the continued work of SENDER will need to be given to the learning processes as the project advances to the implementation phase.

7.1. *Maximizing Renewable Energy Sources*

- High support among most participants
- However, users will be wary of committing before they have a clear understanding of the risk of inconvenience (even if there is none)
- Users will operate on a mental map of which appliances have flexibility potential, and which do not. These should be the focus of enrolment and implementation phase in SENDER
- Such mental maps also contain which routines (i.e. washing clothes, bathing kids, making dinner, charging EV) have flexibility potential and not
- Engaging in demand response in order to “help the grid” (i.e. alleviating congestion) did not resonate strongly in discussions, and tended to receive negative comments. Monetary and environmental arguments are more relevant
- The concept of storage was popular and seen as a solution against inconvenience of load shifting
- This indicates the mental maps of users can be expanded to also include this, often less intuitive, concept of load shifting, not only limited to battery storage, but also to thermal (water/space) storage and the concept of Building as a Battery

7.2. *Building as a Battery (BaaB)*

- Users would be concerned about the relationship between user control and autonomy of the SENDER solutions that is posed by this concept
- When discussing BaaB users generally had a very wide repertoire of opinions, from positive to negative
- This indicates that for users to be able to accept the concept of BaaB in everyday life, this requires negotiation with the system about the level of autonomy and control
- Quite simply, users will not accept anything less than ultimate control, even though a level of autonomy can be given to the system based on negotiations

- Users will allow control over certain appliances to be relinquished most of the time, but the desire to have an override option remains strong
- The reason for this is that even though routine is strong, once in a while something will happen (i.e. sickness, emergencies, etc.) which will require an override
- Paradoxically, even though users were not so eager to relinquish control, neither are they eager to have a system in their lives that requires them to respond very often to requests and notifications
- Some were interested in a central screen on the wall in the house, which did not require logging on so guests/children would be able to use it if necessary
- Having it on the phone and “having to carry it around” and respond to “beeping in your pocket at all times of the day” brought on negative sentiments with some users
- Users were interested in having some way of being aware when and which kinds of decisions were made by the building management system
- Some users were worried about having to “engage too much”, and that if they were less engaged, they miss out on for instance economic benefits. This indicates a “set and forget” mode for the less engaged users should be made possible, to make sure they do not feel robbed of benefits
- As a rule, one user mentioned that 80% of optimization should be done automatically

7.3. *Peer-to-peer Trading*

- A topic which was overall connected with mild positive interest, some curiosity, and quite a bit of confusion
- People have many questions regarding P2P trading, spanning from legal aspects to practical matters of sharing connections (as opposed to trading via a legacy market) and settlement.
- This topic was considered in the most positive terms when it was described as the option to provide neighbors with surplus electricity
- P2P trading was considered a way to avoid sending it back to the grid and the electricity supplier, thereby “robbing” them of a trade
- For this reason, users were most positively inclined to a P2P network that directly connects neighbors
- As evident in the above, many ideas and connotations that people have about P2P can be far removed from the reality in which it is to be employed by SENDER, and this will require a highly developed and focused messaging for them to not have the wrong idea
- In general, P2P trading as a concept creates a lot of confusion with almost all respondents.
- Some were concerned that P2P would cause neighbors to become “business partners” and that this could make relationships in the neighborhood more complicated; it is better with the “faceless grid”
- Some people were completely against P2P, and considered it a rather useless concept, mainly due to the small amounts in question
- Some concern was also noted here in relation to how much time and effort this trading would require, or if it was more or less automatic; the latter option being the preferable one

- Ideas of short-travelled electricity, prosuming and islanding was popular within Austrian discussions. Spanish discussions focused on energy communities as cooperatives, a way of cultivating stronger independence from central energy suppliers
- Selling to neighbors was only preferable if the compensation was at minimum the same as selling to the grid

7.4. *EV Charging*

- In many ways, the car is just another appliance, and can be considered another asset in the portfolio of household appliances
- Similar to the case of appliances and control/autonomy discussion from the BaaB topic, there is a need with most users to clarify the role of the EV as a DR asset through an initial negotiation to set some ground rules
- In general, users are comfortable with the idea that they do not need their mobility at all times and that especially evening and nighttime has flexibility potential without causing inconvenience
- However, some users considered everything up to this discussion “insignificant personal sacrifices” but would draw the line at relinquishing control over the “extremely expensive car in the garage”. This indicates some users have a different relationship with their car, and this may cause a lower flexibility potential in these cases
- Most users were more pragmatic, however, as one hardly ever have to take long trips unexpectedly
- Users would be OK as long as they had 15% to go to the store unannounced and had the possibility to override in the event of planning longer trips
- EV flexibility is connected to many contingencies, like ability to plan, battery size, distance to work, store and other facilities, number of cars
- Routine-based activities (work, showering, etc.), time of day and work situation would also influence EV flexibility potential
- Participating in V2G was considered difficult if the car was not in the driveway during the day

7.5. *Additional information to the forecasting algorithm*

- People seem to this providing additional information somehow (via an app or linking calendars) *sounds* like a good idea in general, but not applicable to themselves
- One reason for this is that people are not generally confident they will have a structured enough life to be able to give the algorithm much help
- A second reason that relates to calendars is that people report not using calendars
- One person said they had a structured enough life, but that when children come home again it would be difficult
- This idea of helping the algorithm generally seemed to bring people to conclude that this needs to be simpler, like a home/away-notifier

- Together with a reporting app the home/away-notifier could possibly be used for giving notice ahead of time for arriving or leaving the home, typically with a timeframe within one day

7.6. Health and safety monitoring

- In general, people did not seem to think using the SENDER sensor suite for health and safety purposes was a good idea
- First of all, there was some general skepticism towards the concept of the digital twin, which people seem to instinctively link to poor privacy and the linking of data with specific people and activities
- This has implications for how this is explained in the early phases of the demonstration phase.
- People have a general skepticism towards the algorithm reacting to abnormal situations, as they have little trust the algorithm will get this right
- People do not consider push notifications or SMS messages as mode of notification of health and safety related events secure enough
- These kinds of services are not considered relevant to electricity management, and would rather turn to a professional security firm for such services
- One small niche where the sensor suite was suggested useful in the home was temperature notification, or a “frost alarm”, relevant especially in Finland where frozen pipes are sometimes a problem

7.7. EV charging and additional information UI for users

- Another monitor/user interface for EV-charging and related information made some respondents worry about information overload
- Users are in general not happy about having to install “yet another app”
- Some users report they would not need this since they “just charge during the night anyway”
- In the case where there was added functionality, not just more information, this could make the proposal more interesting
- The reason for this is that it could make users able to plug in at any time without having to worry about charging during high demand periods
- An added UI related to EV-charging and information would be more attractive if it could link to other devices and UIs in the eco-system surrounding the EV

7.8. Home intervention – practical issues

- People are generally unconcerned about the practical intervention of installers and installing of equipment, however:
- People are not always on the same page about what is the fuse cabinet, or where the smart meter is. This could easily cause confusion and should be considered when planning installations

- Worst case scenario is users not understanding access must be given inside the house as in some cases metering and other electricity equipment is located outside
- In some cases, people would have problem with “holes in their walls”, and this could be related to owning vs. renting
- People were positively inclined to having installers survey existing equipment “to make sure it’s working”. Possible opportunity for positive reinforcement
- Some people will demand information about what SENDER devices use in terms of electricity and bandwidth. If they notice anything off after installation, SENDER will be blamed
- If users have modern equipment installed already, they may be reluctant to having it removed or altered
- If the method of controlling certain aspects of the household change, this could bring about a sense of loss of control
- Some respondents were skeptical towards gadgets emitting too much light, especially in bedrooms
- Some people did in fact not have Wi-Fi, as they only used their phone’s hotspot mode for internet

7.9. Final questions. What motives?

- Environmental factors are motivating but is always weighed up against economic incentives.
- Other factors, like using electricity more sensible, like for instance sharing with neighbors is a motivating factor as well, even without economic incentives
- If economic factors become too pressing, at some point environmental motivations will not be relevant because there will “be no choice”
- Concerns about the health of the grid is in most cases subordinate to the other motivations, as it “becomes too abstract”

8. *Conclusions*

This deliverable has presented findings from the co-creation process in the SENDER project. End users were enrolled into the co-creation process by the help of the use cases developed in D2.4, and user engagement about SENDER solutions were secured by exposing them through semi-structured discussion in workshops to descriptions of these solutions in narrative form as they would appear in an everyday life setting of a household equipped with the SENDER solutions. An analysis of this data and its findings was published in D2.2 workshop report, which was a preliminary version of this deliverable that served as a first look at the information gathered from end users in the co-creation process.

This deliverable has built on the work done in D2.2 and complemented it with a thorough analysis of the co-creation process in SENDER and presents lessons and conclusions about how this process has impacted and served the solution development phase of the project thus far. In order to give a verdict about how this process has the merit of being called co-creation, a review of co-creation literature was presented as well, and allowed us to place the co-creation process in SENDER on the rather wide map of the field that is co-creation. The co-creation process in the SENDER project can be characterized as knowledge co-creation, as the iteration of use cases was thoroughly a co-creation process with input from end users and other stakeholders through CCSG #1 and #2.

Finally, adding to the already extensive list of findings and recommendations from D2.2 workshops report, this deliverable also includes a second round of data in the form of input from end users gathered through the preparatory interviews done in conjunction with the second CCSG. These interviews provided input on more questions and concerns that did arise in the run-up to the implementation phase, and as such will provide especially relevant information for the work that now being undertaken in WP7. In adding an analysis of this data and presenting its results, this deliverable presents the definitive summary of findings and recommendations from WP2, marking the end of the work package and the implementation of the co-creation process.

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10. Appendix

10.1 SENDER Use-case scenarios

General introduction

The SENDER project is a research project under the EU Horizon 2020 programme. It is focused on making better use of our electricity resources by exploiting the flexibility in everyday life, but without relying too much on the need for changes in our behaviour and the way we live our lives day to day.

With the help of IT, Internet and wireless communication, solutions being developed in SENDER and installed in households, will monitor the use of household appliances like water heaters, ovens and air conditioning, lighting, and indoor temperature and weather. This information will then be compared to conditions in the energy markets, the weather forecast, available electricity resources, and local consumption levels.

This results in the creation of a detailed profile, or “construct”, based on household electricity use over time. This “digital twin” of the household will function as a virtual model of its electricity consumption.

These constructs will also contain information about each household’s “comfort profile”, meaning that as occupants interact dynamically with appliances and indoor heating and cooling systems, it will know when it is possible to make adjustments and when it needs to leave you in charge.

Thus, the small but numerous contributions provided by exploiting the gaps in consumption activity across many households, combined with highly accurate predictions about energy consumption, will enable better decision making across ever larger parts of the grid, enabling more efficient electricity use and better use of less stable, renewable energy sources like wind and solar power.

The goal of this workshop is to hear from you, as the future users of these solutions, and what your immediate thoughts and impressions of them are.

We are going to take you through 4 different scenarios of everyday life in a near future where these solutions are present, and some of their effects can be experienced.

It is important to note that we are interested in every impression you may have, that means you can be curious and have questions, you can be inspired and share your ideas, and you can be sceptical and share concerns. In other words, if this is the dumbest idea you have ever heard, this is the place to say so!

There is no need for any expertise about energy or energy technology, as the topic here is how these solutions would fit into YOUR everyday life and electricity consumption, something which you are

already experts of! There are absolutely no right or wrong answers, and no stupid questions. What we aim for is an open discussion where you can convey your ideas, questions, and concerns.

As we move forward with the project and start to develop these technologies in the near future, your feedback will be an important part of the development process. But remember that we are in a very early, exploratory phase of the project, and many of the solutions we are going to talk about today do not exist yet and may be configured differently once they are developed and implemented in the demonstration. So, thank you for joining us in exploring the possibilities of a smarter energy future!

Scenario 1: Maximizing renewable electricity use, reducing cost and emissions

You live in a house connected to local renewable energy sources. The local community is equipped with a windmill park, and several houses in your neighbourhood are equipped with solar panels. This serves your community with a large part of its electricity. However, these local, renewable resources are not able to produce electricity all the time. Solar panels usually produce most of their electricity during the day, and windmills mostly during winter. This means they sometimes need to be supplemented by more conventional sources of energy in the form of some coal, natural gas, and nuclear power, sometimes imported via the central grid from regions of Europe far away, like Poland, Germany, or France. If you could time your consumption to when the local assets are producing, you could save money on the electricity bill as well as making sure consumption is renewable.

Thankfully, through the SENDER project, your house is equipped with a management and monitoring system, connected via the SENDER gateway to many of your appliances, like your EV charger, water heater, and heating/air-conditioner. You yourself are also equipped with an app that can convey messages from your house (i.e. the management and monitoring system) to you, and in this way the house can tell you about the current demand levels and prices, allowing you to synchronize consumption with local production and low prices. How would you go about doing this?

Discussion and follow-up questions

- Q 1.1: What are your main uses of electricity? Is this something that can be moved to other times?
- Q 1.2: (i.e. moving consumption) if it can resolve a grid congestion? What if it reduces the network cost?
- Q 1.3: Would you be interested in provided this service if it made it more likely that a larger share of renewables was used in a certain day?

Scenario 2: Building as a Battery (BaaS)

It is 07:45 in the morning, and as the last person leaving your household you lock the door behind you as you leave for work. The building management system realises at this point that there is no one home. Based on past experience, and knowing that this is a regular workday, the management system is fairly certain that you won't be home for at least eight more hours. While you are away, it is now in control of the heating and cooling facilities in your house. Since it is also connected to the cloud through the SENDER gateway, it provides these appliances as a flexibility service to your local network operator.

Usually, at this time in the morning, many people have been showering before work, and there is a lot of demand to replenish hot water. The electricity supplier tries to do this in a manner that exploits only renewable energy resources. Since it is not enough renewables to heat all the tanks in the neighbourhood at once without using conventional power, through the SENDER gateway it asks to put your water heater in a queue.

Later, as it happens on this day, around 2 pm, the network operator notices that there is a sudden and unexpected increase in demand, and the power lines are nearly congested. It contacts your building management system through the gateway, and requests that your house stops consuming electricity for the time being. Since your building management system knows you will not be home for another couple of hours, it grants the request and shuts off your heating/cooling for 60 minutes.

Discussion and follow-up questions

Q 2.1: Are you OK with these decisions being made for you? Even if you would not notice any effect?

Q 2.2: If not, would you want it to ask you permission every time? I.e. through an app

Q 2.3: Will you need to know in real time and approve for each instance, or is it fine if you can just review it at a later time?

Scenario 3: Peer-to-peer trading

In your neighbourhood, not everyone has the benefit of having solar panels on their roof. However, imagine you are one of those who have. Usually, during the day when you and your family is busy with work and school, the house sits empty while the solar panels produce an abundance of electricity. The management system does what it can to consume most of the electricity that's being produced and translate it into comfortable indoor temperatures and hot water in the tank. However, sometimes there is a surplus in the production that the house is simply not able to consume. In these cases, the electricity goes back into the grid.

However, since not just your house, but every house in the neighbourhood is equipped with the SENDER energy management system and connected together in the cloud, your house is able to ask your neighbour's house if it needs some of that electricity that your solar panels are currently producing. Lacking a panel rig, the only alternative for your neighbour's house is to go on the regular market to get the power it needs, and so it is happy to pay you for some of your solar power.

Discussion and follow-up questions

- Q 3.1: Would you need compensation for putting the electricity you yourself cannot use back into the grid? (PVs can be an expensive investment.)
- Q 3.2: What about providing your neighbour's house with your surplus electricity instead?
- Q 3.3: What if it was the other way around? Would you be flexible in order to make sure you consume your neighbour's surplus electricity?

Scenario 4: EV charging

You come home from work and plug in your EV, which is at around 60% charged, since you are fortunate enough to be able to charge it at your workplace. The first item on your agenda is to clean some kids and then some clothes, and then to make dinner for everybody. There is still some power being produced in your solar panels, but not enough to charge the car, re-heat all the water consumption, and make dinner, without also buying from the grid.

This, however, is not a problem. The house management system knows from previous experience that even though there *is* a demand for all these services right now, having fully heated water and a fully charged vehicle is a lower priority than cooking dinner and having a comfortable indoor temperature. This means, even though the car is plugged in and the water in the tank is below set temperature, they have been kindly requested by the management system not to charge yet.

When dinner has been served, and much of the household electricity demand has been served along with it, the management system starts considering filling some of the demand it has postponed. However, afternoon/evening are high demand hours, and the network operator is once again worried about grid congestion. Through the SENDER gateway it requests that your building contributes to keeping demand low for the time being, and for the network operator, every watt counts.

Your management system decides that it can accommodate this request by not charging the car or heating the water tank right now. It even considers using the car to power some of the appliances in the house. However, since you are home it decides to ask your permission before doing anything with the heating/cooling, and you receive a notification where you can grant your permission to allow temperatures to slide for 30 minutes while the grid congestions clears.

Discussion and follow-up questions

- Q 4.1: What do you think about letting the management system take control of your indoor temperature for short periods of time?
- Q 4.2: What if you come home, and the car is at 15%. You have programmed it to charge during the night to save money. Is this feasible?
- Q 4.3: In general, how interested are you in being in control of these processes? What is needed in order for you to trust the energy management system to do it for you?

For extended discussion and abundance of time: additional services

- Motion sensors
- The algo can know when you are there and not, and after a while it will predict when you are there and not
 - The algo will be worried if you aren't moving about when you should
 - The algo will monitor temperature and air quality, and can smell a fire
 - The monitoring system smells carbon monoxide/sees thermal hot spot and can warn you or the fire dpt.
 - The monitoring system realises you are not moving, and after nudging you a few times via your phone calls a relative and/or health care services/police
 - Break-in/unauthorized access via a window or doorway detected. Notifies you and calls the police/security company

10.2 Interview guide for end user's input to CCSG2

The aim of this interview guide is to explore some central questions related to the SENDER Energy Management System, which when installed in your home will be able to make sure the electricity spent within will not go to heating an unoccupied house or to charge EVs when the prices are at their highest. When installed in your home, the SENDER Gateway uses historical and real-time information about energy markets, temperatures, and presence monitoring to control water and space temperatures and EV charging in order to save energy. It will do this while making sure you are always comfortable when at home, and that your EV, should you have one, is ready to go when you need it. In the following we will cover three scenarios and some practical questions related to the installation of the equipment itself. This will help us to make the finishing touches to the solutions which will be tested in the upcoming demonstration phase, planned for the fall of this year.

1. SCENARIO: Possibility of providing additional information to the forecasting algorithm

The SENDER home monitoring and control system uses information gathered from sensors in the home to predict the chances of you and your family being home or not on the upcoming day. For instance, based on experience, on Sunday it already knows that Mondays represent a high likelihood of the house being empty from 0900-1500, and it can decide to reduce consumption in some appliances. The more information the algorithm can base its calculations on, the better the prediction. However, for instance in the age of the home office society, past experiences may not always reliably predict our plans for tomorrow. What would you say if there was a way for you to provide some information about future plans so that the algorithm could safely conclude whether or not anyone would be home for the day?

Follow up to explore the practical implications for user:

- Reporting functionality in an app
- Vacation mode
- Outlook calendar access
- School schedule

2. SCENARIO: Health and safety monitoring

As mentioned, the SENDER home monitoring and control system uses information gathered from sensors to determine if there is someone in the house or not. These sensors can measure temperature, luminosity, humidity, and motion. They could for instance be located in the electrical outlet or in doors/windows, or as motion detectors in certain areas of the home. This sensing capability makes it possible to make an instruction for the algorithm to react to certain conditions in the home. For instance, if it assumes there is a high likelihood someone is home, but at the same time is detecting no movement, this could indicate someone in need of assistance. This could be useful as an added safety

measure in cases of home care, but it can also be useful in cases where someone is in the house that should not be, as would be the case in a break-in. The system could respond by sending you in-app notifications, or warning security services/authorities directly.

Follow up:

- Will users be OK with a system that is looking for anomalous behavior?
- How should the system warn/notify us?

3. EV charging

The final scenario is related to EV-charging. It may be possible to provide a dashboard for additional information about and control capability for EV charging. It will be accessible online, comes in addition to the app, and will provide historical data about past charging sessions, current charging profile, and the possibility of setting a minimum charge level. Where are you most interested in charging your car and receiving this information, at home or at a public charge point?

4. Home intervention – practical issues

In order to set up the SENDER system at the household, an installer will need to visit and install some equipment like the SENDER Gateway, sensors, plugs, etc. This may cause some small disturbance in the home as the equipment needs a permanent location close to power and Internet, where it can be continuously connected to both power and Internet. Some thermostats in the home may need to be changed, as well as controllers for these thermostats added. The installer may need access to the electrical board of the home and the Smart Meter inside it. As mentioned, sensors may measure temperature, luminosity, humidity and motion, and it too needs continuous access to power (i.e., it steals a plug) and Internet (Wi-Fi). If possible, SENDER would also ask the homeowner to provide information about the electrical board (take a picture) and about HVAC models and other, existing smart appliances, if there are any. What do users think about this?

Checklist:

- a. Installing of gateway
- b. OK to use Internet?
- c. OK to leave gateway plugged in?
- d. OK to replace thermostat?
- e. OK to install controllers for thermostat?
- f. Access to electrical board and smart meter?
- g. OK that sensors measure temperature, luminosity, humidity and motion?
- h. OK that sensors steal a plug and Wi-Fi?
- i. OK to audit equipment and other smart appliances?

5. Final questions

But why are we doing all this? Mainly because of three reasons. First, it can reduce your electricity bill. By using market data and information about when you are away, it can optimize electricity consumption, making sure you do not use electricity you do not need. Second, if you have renewable energy production at home, like solar PV, it can make sure you use this as efficiently as possible, making sure appliances use your renewables when it is available. Finally, all the small contributions from many SENDER-capable households will make it possible to schedule the electricity system more precisely, so that it is able to make better use of renewables and still maintain high levels of stability – and low cost – in the grid. Which of these reasons are most compelling to you?